

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a large, light blue, rounded shape resembling a speech bubble or a cloud. Below this shape is a stylized blue wave. Underneath the wave is a series of dark blue circles of varying sizes, arranged in a slightly curved line.

EVOLVE2CARE

**D5.1– Project Management
Handbook**

WP5 – Project Coordination and
Management

January 2025 | Version 3.0

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the European Union

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission

EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
WP	Work Package
PB	Plenary Board or General Assembly

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this Deliverable is to present the project management framework of the EVOLVE2CARE project, including all managerial and operational activities planned for the project's entire duration. This deliverable will serve as a practical guide to clearly define workflows and rules that partners must follow during the project's activities, ensuring the highest quality standards are upheld and enhancing project management quality control, operational, and data management procedures.

This deliverable serves as handbook for all members of the Project to effectively search for information about the managerial and operational processes of EVOLVE2CARE. As the project progresses, information may be changed or extended to reflect the alterations in the processes. Furthermore, several links have been added to this document as a quick reference point. These links are accessible only to verified members of the project.

Furthermore, in the second Annex, the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the entire project is presented. The DMP outlines how project partners will monitor data processing during the project and after its completion. It includes a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP) detailing the lifecycle of project data and activities related to its processing and protection.

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1. Introduction

This document outlines the management structure of the EVOLVE2CARE Project, including quality control procedures and strategies to address potential barriers and risks that may arise during project activities. It serves as the project management framework for all partners.

1.1. Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE is a project to create a market-driven framework that leverages Living Lab (LL) networks to address barriers to innovation and commercialization in transitional care. It connects stakeholders like innovators, hospitals, insurers, and policy makers to validate HealthTech solutions.

The project unfolds in three phases:

- **Phase 1:** Identify stakeholder needs and design the AccelUP marketplace to match innovators with LLs.
- **Phase 2:** Develop modules and services for the AccelUP platform.
- **Phase 3:** Conduct experiments in real-world settings, providing resources and payment vouchers to LLs.

AccelUP serves as the central platform, fostering collaboration and streamlining the innovation process.

1.2. Description of WP5

The primary aim of WP5, led by AUTH, is to guarantee the successful implementation of the project. Its specific objectives include:

- Overseeing and managing the overall execution of the project.
- Ensuring adherence to the legal, contractual, financial, and reporting obligations outlined by Horizon Europe and the European Commission.
- Delivering the project on schedule and within budget while promoting effective communication between participants and work packages (WPs) and maintaining correspondence with the European Commission.
- Addressing technical, intellectual property rights (IPR), innovation management, and compliance with the data management plan.

1.3. Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This document provides a detailed guide for managing, organizing, and executing the project, with an emphasis on efficient coordination, delivering high-quality results, and adhering to established standards. It details the processes, tools, and frameworks that guide the project's workflow, covering everything from planning and communication to reporting and quality assurance.

1.4. Structure

D5.1 “Project Management Handbook” includes 8 sections that cover the below areas:

- **Section 1 Introduction:** A brief description of the document’s purpose and structure.
- **Section 2 Project Meetings:** Guidelines for organizing, conducting, and documenting project meetings.
- **Section 3 Project Management Tools and Guidelines:** Details on tools and strategies for efficient project management.
- **Section 4 Document Management:** Covers document classification, standards, templates, and compliance with data protection guidelines.
- **Section 5 Dissemination, Communication and Outreach:** Strategies for sharing project results with stakeholders and the public.
- **Section 6 Scientific Publications:** Framework for publishing research outcomes in academic and professional settings.
- **Section 7 Project Reporting and Financing:** Defines eligible activities and costs, reporting templates, financial procedures, and timelines.
- **Section 8 Data Management Plan:** A brief description of EVOLVE2CARE’s Data Management Plan.
- **Section 9 Quality Assessment:** Establishes quality expectations, roles, and procedures for quality assurance and control, including risk management practices.
- **Section 10 Project Leadership and Roles:** Provides a description of the external project’s advisors (Advisory Board and External Ethics Advisor) , their role and the actions that need to be taken by the Consortium.
- **Section 11 Performance Metrics:** The KPIs and the partners responsible for each one are presented.
- **Section 12 Conclusions:** The conclusions drawn from this handbook are showcased.

Annex 1 also includes a detailed Data Management Plan, outlining the protocols for handling, storing, and sharing project data.

2. Project Meetings

2.1. Types of meetings

2.1.1. Stand-up meetings

EVOLVE2CARE hosts "Stand-Up meetings" which will take place online (teleconferences) every two weeks. The meetings are expected to last no more than 30 minutes and are scheduled and run by the AUTH as project Coordinator.

The goal of these meetings is to present and discuss the ongoing work of the project and also address any major issues and find solutions. This meeting is open to everyone to participate in and is important to be attended by the WP leaders. Their role is to inform the consortium shortly about:

- The ongoing work of each WP
- Expected contribution/support from the consortium
- Any risks/blocking factors and mitigation measures
- The envisaged plan for the next two weeks

2.1.2. Plenary Meetings

The primary platform for communication and collaboration in EVOLVE2CARE is the Consortium Plenary Meetings. These meetings will be held every six months, and require the participation of representatives from all partners.

- The purpose of the Consortium Plenary Meetings is to:
- Review and present the current progress of the project.
- Outline upcoming tasks and schedule the next steps.
- Address technical challenges and identify solutions.
- Foster collaboration among partners and resolve integration issues.
- Refine and update the overall project vision.

2.1.2.1. Plenary meeting scheduling

During each plenary meeting, the consortium will decide on the location and potential dates for the next meeting. The hosting organization will be responsible for arranging and booking an appropriate venue and must notify the consortium **at least one month in advance** to facilitate travel arrangements. Additionally, it is recommended that the hosting organization provide details on how to access the meeting location.

2.1.2.1. Attendance reporting

All partners are required to notify the hosting organization of the names and number of participants attending the physical meeting **at least one week in advance**. This information should be submitted through the meeting's **Attendance List**.

2.1.3. WP and Task meetings

In addition to Stand-up and Plenary Meetings, partners may organize meetings focused on specific Work Packages or tasks (scientific, technical, or otherwise) to enhance collaboration and speed up progress. The entire Consortium should be informed, and the Project Coordinator should attend to ensure proper coordination.

2.1.3.1. WP/Task meetings scheduling

The meeting organizer should:

1. Propose potential dates and times for the meeting using a tool like Doodle and confirm the date and time with the highest availability.
2. Email attendees with the meeting details, including the date, time, and link.
3. Optionally, include the Teams meeting link in the description and invite the EVOLVE2CARE mailing list (evolve2care@googlegroups.com) as a guest.

2.2. Meeting Procedures

2.2.1. Current recurring meetings

Current available meeting links are show in the below table:

Table 1 EVOLVE2CARE's fixed meetings

Meeting Title	Occurrence	Link
Stand-up meeting	Every 2 weeks on Tuesday	https://teams.microsoft.com/l/meetup-join/19%3ac2040369c9a4493bacadaa7ccc2dad3b%40thread.tacv2/1732271968503?context=%7b%22Tid%22%3a%2240fac2eb-f379-4b09-b655-243ff8c9739d%22%2c%22Oid%22%3a%224b0d32ca-6bea-4659-b10f-092e4ad3ac1a%22%7d

<p>Status Meeting for WP1</p>	<p>Weekly on Friday</p>	<p>https://teams.microsoft.com/l/meetup-join/19%3ameeting_MTdkOWQzYjUtN2U4Ny00OWQyLWFmMTgtMDcyMzI1YWw5ZmY4%40thread.v2/0?context=%7b%22Tid%22%3a%22cc03f2a3-2f02-4826-85a6-a6277c875551%22%2c%22Oid%22%3a%22a80bfa4a-6de0-4e0e-a757-040bba9ae09a%22%7d</p>
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2.2.2. Minutes of Meetings

The meeting host is responsible for preparing and distributing written minutes as the official record of decisions made. A draft of the minutes will be shared with all members **within 10 days of the meeting**.

3. Project Management Tools and Guidelines

3.1. Project Management Tools

3.1.1. MS Teams

The main EVOLVE2CARE project management tool of the project is MS Teams. There is a separate channel for each Work Package, named after the number of each WP and the leading responsible partner

Figure 1 EVOLVE2CARE Teams Channels

Within each WP folder there are 4 different tabs. The WP Deliverables and Tasks are included in the corresponding Tasks, in a Planner view, including columns for *Not Started*, *In Progress*, *On Hold*, *Delayed*, *Closed* Tasks and Deliverables, accordingly. For each Task and Deliverable, a responsible person is assigned by the WP leader.

Figure 2 EVOLVE2CARE Teams WPs Structure

Each WP has its own files under the Files tab. All deliverables should be uploaded in the files folder inside a folder entitled "Deliverables".

The Deliverables folder in all WPs should follow the below structure:

- **Working versions:** the folder where the responsible partner prepares the deliverable for review
- **Reviews:** the folder where the reviewer adds their feedback
- **Submitted:** The final version of the deliverable that was submitted in the EU

Figure 3 EVOLVE2CARE Teams Deliverables Folder Structure

It is the WP leader's responsibility to organize the rest of the items in the files folder.

3.1.2. Slack

A Slack workspace has been created for EVOLVE2CARE for daily communication among the partners of the Project. This workspace has six channels dedicated to each Work Package where the partners are encouraged to discuss and share their thoughts on the progress of the project. Furthermore, the channels General and Random have been set up for topics that are not directly linked to the Work Packages of the Project. Each channel has a detailed description of each role.

Figure 4 EVOLVE2CARE Slack channels

Due to the automatic deletion of messages and files after 90 days in the free version of Slack, the partners are advised to keep records of important files and messages outside of Slack either through email or file sharing in Teams.

3.2. E-mail communication

To streamline communication within the project, mailing lists have been set up. Partners are encouraged to use the relevant Slack channels as the primary communication method to avoid redundant or excessive messaging. The Evolve2Care project mailing list is available at evolve2care@googlegroups.com. The mailing list is used to communicate important project decisions, updates and meeting minutes.

3.2.1. Email standards

Below there are some guidelines for email subject lines to ensure clear communication among consortium members in line with the project's objectives:

- **Always** include the prefix **[EVOLVE2CARE]** at the start of the subject.
- Include the relevant **WP number** if applicable.
- Use the prefix **[Doodle]** if sharing a Doodle link for a meeting.
- Use the prefix **[Action required]** if requesting specific actions.
- Use the prefix **[URGENT]** for matters needing immediate attention.

3.2.2. Contacting consortium members

The [EVOLVE2CARE team contacts.xlsx](#) file, located in the WP5 folder on Microsoft Teams, contains the contact details of all consortium members.

To ensure smooth information flow and keep everyone updated, it is recommended to cc the project management team in bilateral communications.

4. Document management

4.1. Classification of Documents

Deliverables, including documents, must be categorized according to the dissemination levels specified in the Grant Agreement (GA) using the following codes:

- **PU:** Public.
- **CO:** Confidential, restricted to Consortium members (including EC Services).
- **EU-RES:** Classified information: RESTREINT UE (per EC decision 2005/444/EC).
- **EU-CON:** Classified information: CONFIDENTIAL UE (per EC decision 2005/444/EC).
- **EU-SEC:** Classified information: SECRET UE (per EC decision 2005/444/EC).

4.2. Document standards

4.2.1. Allowed document types

Working documents that require further editing by partners should be created using Microsoft Office.

Final versions of documents, such as internal and public deliverables, should be saved and shared as .PDF files (compatible with Adobe Acrobat 7.0 or later).

Other files, including graphics, audio, and video, should use standard formats like .JPG, .PNG, .GIF, .TIFF, .PPT, etc.

4.2.2. Format and style guidelines

The format and style of the official documents of the project should follow the templates (see 5.4) and style guidelines provided by ViLabs.

4.3. Versioning

During document preparation, the following types of intermediate versions may be created:

- **Table of contents (ToC):** Contains main headlines and some detailed topics.
- **Full Draft:** Includes nearly completed sections.

- **Ready-for-Review Version:** Shared with internal reviewers for feedback and edits.
- **Pre-Final Version:** Includes only minor changes, shared with EVOLVE2CARE partners, and submitted to the Project Coordinator for final approval before submission to the EC.

Multiple feedback rounds may be required for each version. When revising documents:

- Use Microsoft Word's Revision Mode to track changes.
- Upload the updated version to the file repository using the correct naming convention.
- The responsible person for the deliverable will incorporate changes into the document.

Version Numbering

- **0 to 0.XX:** Draft working documents.
- **1.00:** Submitted for internal review.
- **2.00:** Revised version after feedback.
- **3.00:** Final version submitted to the European Commission portal.
- **3.00_Open:** Final public version uploaded to the EVOLVE2CARE website, ensuring compliance with Data Protection Regulations.

4.4. Templates

To ensure consistency across the various documents produced, clean and functional templates were developed at the start of the project. The following EVOLVE2CARE document templates have been created and shared with all partners:

- **A4 template:** [evolve2care_a4 template.docx](#)
- **Attendance List template:** [evolve2care_attendanceList_template.docx](#)
- **Deliverable template:** [evolve2care_deliverable template.docx](#)
- **Meeting template:** [evolve2care_meeting template.docx](#)
- **Power Point template:** [evolve2care_ppt template.pptx](#)
- **Deliverable Review template:** [evolve2care_deliverable_internal_review template.docx](#)

The templates can be found in EVOLVE2CARE's Teams path: **EVOLVE2CARE/WP4 (VILABS)/Task4.1 EVOLVE2CARE Dissemination, Communication and Outreach for the Open Calls/Templates**

5. Dissemination, Communication and Outreach

5.1. Project Branding

The main elements that define the brand of EVOLVE2CARE are the Logo and the Colour scheme.

All dissemination materials that follow the style guidelines have been produced and can be found in EVOLVE2CARE's Teams within **WP4 (VILABS)/Task 4.1 - EVOLVE2CARE Dissemination, Communication and Outreach for the Open Calls/Materials**.

5.1.1. Logo and Colour scheme usage

All partners should follow the brand guidelines when creating materials for the project. The logo and the colour scheme are the central pieces of the EVOLVE2CARE brand. The logo can be seen below:

Figure 5 EVOLVE2CARE logo

The logo can be found here: [Project logo](#)

The colour scheme of the project logo, along with the complementary colours, is the following:

- Primary Colour: #366087 [Lapis Lazuli]
- Secondary Colour 1: # 65A5D3 [Air Superiority Blue]
- Secondary Colour 2: # 95D3EA [Sky Blue]
- Secondary Colour 3: #E2FDFF [Light Cyan]
- Extra Colour 1: #57C3A6 [Mint]
- Extra Colour 2: #C5DCA0 [Tea Green]

5.1.2. Brand Book

The project's **Brand Book** provides extensive information and guidelines about the project's visual identity and its properties.

5.2. Project website – Social media channels

5.2.1. Website

The project's website has been officially launched in October 2024 (M1), under the domain name <https://evolve2care.eu/>.

5.2.2. Social Media Pages

EVOLVE2CARE utilises a variety of social media pages. **Facebook and LinkedIn platforms and YouTube** were strategically chosen to disseminate the work of EVOLVE2CARE.

The partners are **strongly encouraged to interact with the project's social media posts via their organisation's social media accounts.**

Facebook Page

The Facebook page of the project is titled [Evolve2Care](#).

LinkedIn page

The LinkedIn page of the project is titled [EVOLVE2CARE HorizonEU](#).

YouTube channel

The channel is named [EVOLVE2CARE Project HorizonEU](#).

More information can be found in EVOLVE2CARE's **D4.1 "Dissemination, Communication and Outreach Strategy and Materials"** in Section 2.4.3 Online Channels.

5.2.3. Content update

ViLabs is responsible for updating the content of the website and the social media pages. All partners have to communicate with ViLabs for any project-related activities that they organise or participate so that they collaboratively plan the dissemination for these activities. It is advised that the responsible partner informs ViLabs for the upcoming activities or events at least 2 weeks before the actual date.

5.3. Events Calendar

An Events Calendar has been created in the EVOLVE2CARE Teams workspace under the WP4 channel. This calendar will serve as a quick reference point to keep track of the identified events where EVOLVE2CARE can be promoted. What is more, the calendar is meant to assist carrying out proper reporting of dissemination, communication and outreach efforts from partners.

Partners are encouraged to add relevant events (whether they plan to attend or not) to this calendar.

5.4. Reporting and Feedback

Upon the completion of any dissemination, communication and outreach activity, partners fill out the reporting form to ensure accurate bookkeeping of effort. The form is stored in the project repository under this link: [evolve2care_dissemination_communication_and_outreach_reporting_form.xlsx](#)

To maintain proper reporting throughout the project, partners will need to:

- Respond to ViLabs’s bi-monthly requests to report activities and efforts.
- Notify the WP4 leader (ViLabs) whenever a new activity opportunity arises, so it can be documented and support provided (e.g., guidelines, tips, etc.).

Furthermore, when an external party contacts a partner to discuss regarding a potential collaboration, the partner should follow the following *guidelines*:

- Notify VILABS about the collaboration offer, ensuring that other partners are included in the conversation if needed. A call can be arranged to discuss the next steps.
- Report the meeting on the online [evolve2care_dissemination_communication_and_outreach_reporting_form.xlsx](#)

5.5. EVOLVE2CARE Target groups

EVOLVE2CARE partners have identified the project target groups and assigned the main responsible partners for communicating the project and its results as presented below:

- **TG#1: Innovators** - Sploro
- **TG#2: Accelerators/Investors** - AV
- **TG#3: Living Labs** - ENoLL
- **TG#4.1: End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)** –AUTH
- **TG#4.2: End-users (Individuals)** – AUTH
- **TG#5: Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies**– Vilabs
- **TG#6: EU Initiatives** – Sploro

More information about the project target groups can be found in [evolve2care_target_audiences.docx](#).

5.6. Participation in external events

Below we present the guidelines that partners need to take into account when participating in external events:

Before the event

Partners should inform the Project Coordinator (AUTH) and WP4 Leader (VILABS) about the identified opportunity in order to plan collaboratively the dissemination activities and prepare any needed material (e.g., leaflets, roll-ups). Additionally, they should update the Event Calendar (see 5.3.).

During the event

Partners should collect photos and videos, from all EVOLVE2CARE activities and send them to AUTH and VILABS to be used in publicity materials (e.g., newsletters). They should ensure that this material is not breaching any third party-intellectual property rights.

After the event

All dissemination actions and activities should be reported in the necessary form (see 5.4.)

5.7. Creation of dissemination material

If a partner wishes to create their own communication, dissemination and outreach material they should follow the below steps:

1. Include the project's logo and follow the colour scheme and brand identity guidelines as defined in the Brand book (see 5.1.)
2. Include the appropriate acknowledgement for the EU funding (see 6.6)
3. Send the material to VILABS for review and approval.

6. Scientific Publications

The publication process is overseen by the Publication Review Board as defined in Section 10.2.

6.2. Responsibilities of first author

The first author is the lead author with the responsibility of the manuscript or abstract.

The lead author has the following duties and responsibilities:

- Leads the writing group and drafts the initial version of the manuscript or abstract.
- Ensures clear and effective communication within the writing group. When circulating a draft, they must outline the target journal's or conference's guidelines, specify the required feedback, and set clear timelines and a submission deadline.
- Monitors progress and ensures that all co-authors meet the full conditions of authorship by the end of the writing process.
- Corresponds with the journal's editor(s) (unless otherwise agreed) and coordinates necessary revisions after the review process.
- Informs the PRB and the writing group once the publication receives final approval.
- Forwards the published version of the paper to the PRB and writing group.

6.3. Last author

The last author is regarded as a special position and is usually assigned to the senior supervising researcher. This should be the project coordinator of EVOLVE2CARE, Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, unless otherwise agreed.

6.4. Paper submission

The process for submitting a paper is the following:

- The lead author submits the proposed publication to the PRB for approval.
- The PRB reviews the submission and informs the lead author of their decision within two (2) days.

- WP leaders and lead investigators are contacted regarding the publication and invited to act as co-authors or nominate a suitable co-author based on the guidelines below.
- The PRB must be electronically notified whenever a manuscript is submitted to a journal.
- Following peer review, the manuscript is revised, and the PRB is notified upon re-submission.
- If accepted for publication, the PRB and WP4 leader must be informed, and a PDF of the published article must be sent for dissemination.
- In case of rejection, the PRB must be notified along with the journal's justification for rejection.
- The PRB and WP4 leader must also be notified when an abstract is submitted to a conference and whether it is accepted (specifying oral or poster presentation) or rejected.
- A copy of the PowerPoint or poster presentation of an accepted abstract must be sent to the PRB and WP4 leader for archiving and dissemination.

For accepted publications, additional required information must be provided for upload to the EU portal.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Add Publication". The form contains the following fields and options:

- Type of PID (repository) *
- PID (publisher version of record) *
- PID of deposited publication
- Type of publication *
- Link to publication
- Title of the scientific publication *
- Authors *
- Title of the Journal or equivalent
- Number
- ISSN or eISSN
- Publisher *
- Month of publication
- Year of publication
- Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication * Yes No
- Peer-reviewed * Yes No
- PID of Book
- Book title
- Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project? Yes No
- Article processing costs that will be charged to the project
- License type

Figure 6 Required info from publications for reporting in EU portal

6.5. Empirical Papers

Empirical research papers may result from data collected by members of EVOLVE2CARE which were the result of research that took place during the writing of a project deliverable or across specific tasks and/or different work packages.

The authorship of these papers should include:

- The Work Package members and Work Task Leader (if specified) involved in the data collection and analysis
- The Work Package Leader (usually one individual, but more if their contribution can justify it).
- Scientific Coordinator (usually one individual, but more if their contribution can justify it)
- Project Coordinator (usually one individual, but more if their contribution can justify it).

6.6. Acknowledgements

As a general guideline, scientific and/or technical publications must adhere to specific requirements set by the European Commission concerning the acknowledgment of EU funding. Consequently, contributing authors should ensure their papers **always include the following statement:**

“This [paper/work/article] is conducted in the context of EVOLVE2CARE project, that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101158152.”

If an additional disclaimer is required, the following statement may be included alongside the funding acknowledgment:

“Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

This also applies to any Scientific Publications that might be produced as an outcome of the work of mini-consortia that will be selected through the Open Calls.

7. Project reporting and financing

The Grant Agreement signed by the EVOLVE2CARE consortium (Nr. 101158152) specifies the terms and conditions applicable to the grant awarded to beneficiaries. The activities funded are the ones described in Annex 1 (Part A and Part B) of the Grant Agreement.

7.2. Eligible and ineligible contributions

The eligible and ineligible contributions of EVOLVE2CARE are described in Article 6 of the Grant Agreement Nr 101158152.

7.3. General procedures and rules for project reporting

According to the EVOLVE2CARE Grant Agreement, the Coordinator must submit technical and financial reports to the EC on each reporting period.

7.3.3. Reporting Periods

The official reporting periods of the EVOLVE2CARE project are the following:

Report 1 (RP No 1): From Month 1 (October 2024) – Month 12 (September 2025), and Report 1 ought to be sent to the coordinators by the 31st of October 2025

Report 2 (RP No 2): From Month 13 (October 2025) – Month 24 (September 2026), and Report 2 ought to be sent to the coordinators by the 31st of October 2026

7.3.4. Reporting Process

The reporting procedure involves the following steps:

Partners (Beneficiaries):

- Submit a six-month report, including updates on their institution's dissemination and exploitation activities during the reporting period, as well as administrative details.
- Maintain a record of their team members timesheets.

WP Leaders:

- Provide a description of work progress within their Work Package (WP) for the Periodic Progress Reports.
- Collect relevant information from the corresponding Task leaders and the involved partner and consolidate them in a coherent description.
- Ensure effective communication within their WP to facilitate information sharing.

Coordinating Institution:

- Compile contributions from all partners and WP Leaders into a consolidated document.
- Submit the final report to the European Commission.

7.3.5. Financial Report Template

The first version of financial report template can be found in the shared Teams workspace: [EVOLVE2CARE Partner Name semester Nr v.1.xlsx](#).

Partner (Select)		AUTH										Status		JUSTIFICATIONS		
		WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	M1-M6	M7-M12	M13-M18	M18-M24	RP1 total	RP2 total				
EXPENSES		PROPOSAL BUDGET					EXPENSES									
AUTH	A. DIRECT PERSONNEL COSTS	24,500.0	59,700.0	38,650.0	15,100.0	24,500.0									underspending	
	B. DIRECT SUBCONTRACTING COSTS														Normal	
	C. DIRECT TRAVEL COSTS		2,400.0	1,200.0	4,800.0	4,800.0									underspending	
	C.2. EQUIPMENT COSTS														Normal	
	C.3. OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES			4,000.0	4,000.0										underspending	
	TOTAL	24,500.0	62,100.0	43,850.0	23,900.0	29,300.0										
	TOTAL including INDIRECT FLAT RATE	30,625.0	77,625.0	54,612.5	29,875.0	36,625.0										
ENOLL	A. DIRECT PERSONNEL COSTS	7,000.0	28,000.0	42,000.0	28,000.0	24,000.0									underspending	
	B. DIRECT SUBCONTRACTING COSTS														underspending	
	C. DIRECT TRAVEL COSTS		1,100.0	1,100.0	4,400.0	6,000.0									underspending	
	C.2. EQUIPMENT COSTS														Normal	
	C.3. OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES														Normal	
	TOTAL	7,000.0	29,100.0	93,100.0	32,400.0	20,000.0										
	TOTAL including INDIRECT FLAT RATE	8,750.0	36,375.0	103,875.0	40,500.0	25,000.0										
AV	A. DIRECT PERSONNEL COSTS	22,395.0	31,120.7	63,775.3	39,865.5	6,767.7									underspending	
	B. DIRECT SUBCONTRACTING COSTS														Normal	
	C. DIRECT TRAVEL COSTS	2,200.0	2,000.0	2,200.0	4,400.0	2,200.0									underspending	
	C.2. EQUIPMENT COSTS														underspending	
	C.3. OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES				4,800.0										underspending	
	TOTAL	24,595.0	33,120.7	72,035.3	44,265.5	8,967.7										
	TOTAL including INDIRECT FLAT RATE	30,743.7	41,400.9	90,044.1	55,231.3	11,209.6										
SPROLO	A. DIRECT PERSONNEL COSTS	10,000.0	89,500.0	10,000.0	10,000.0	10,000.0									underspending	
	B. DIRECT SUBCONTRACTING COSTS														Normal	
	C. DIRECT TRAVEL COSTS	1,125.0	7,875.0												underspending	
	C.2. EQUIPMENT COSTS		750.0												underspending	
	C.3. OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES		4,000.0		1,000.0										underspending	
	TOTAL	11,125.0	102,125.0	10,000.0	11,000.0	10,000.0										
	TOTAL including INDIRECT FLAT RATE	13,906.3	127,656.3	12,500.0	13,750.0	12,500.0										
VILABS	A. DIRECT PERSONNEL COSTS	2,000.0	4,000.0	2,500.0	62,500.0	10,800.0									underspending	
	B. DIRECT SUBCONTRACTING COSTS														Normal	
	C. DIRECT TRAVEL COSTS				4,400.0	1,100.0									underspending	
	C.2. EQUIPMENT COSTS														Normal	
	C.3. OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES														Normal	
	TOTAL	2,000.0	4,000.0	2,500.0	66,900.0	11,900.0										
	TOTAL including INDIRECT FLAT RATE	2,500.0	5,000.0	3,125.0	108,625.0	14,875.0										

Figure 7 EVOLVE2CARE Financial Report Template

The template will be finalized during the interim reporting period.

7.3.6. Currency

Financial statements must be prepared in euros. For beneficiaries and linked third parties whose accounts are maintained in a currency other than the euro, costs must be converted into euros using the average daily exchange rate published in the C series of the Official Journal of the European Union over the reporting period.

If no daily exchange rate is published for the currency in question, the conversion should use the average monthly accounting rates available on the European Commission's website for the relevant reporting period.

8. Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the processes for managing research data from planning through to publication and beyond. It covers stages such as research design, data collection, processing, analysis, publication, dissemination, preservation, and reuse, ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and data protection requirements.

The DMP serves as a self-regulatory tool, ensuring ethical standards, adherence to Horizon Europe guidelines, and principles of research integrity. It applies to all project activities involving data processing and sets out measures for proper data protection. It also ensures that dissemination, methods, tools, and technologies used in the project align with the DMP's ethical standards and legal requirements.

The Data Management Plan can be viewed in detail in Annex 1. As the project progresses the DMP may be updated to reflect changes.

9. Quality assessment

9.2. Quality control of deliverables

All deliverables will be internally reviewed in order to ensure timely production and quality. Some of them may also be reviewed externally. As a result, the following process will be followed:

Assigned Responsibilities

- Each deliverable has a responsible partner as assigned in the DoA.
- The partner responsible assigns contributors and finalizes the ToC, subtasks, and contributions timeline, shared with the Project Coordinator (PC) 6 weeks before the deadline.

Preparation of the Full Draft

- Contributors complete their tasks; the responsible partner integrates them into the Full draft version
- The responsible partner of the deliverable shares the Ready-for-Review Version once the Full draft version is ready.

Review

- The Internal reviewer provides feedback within 1 week. The assigned internal reviewers can be found in [evolve2care_list_of_deliverable_reviewers_v1.xlsx](#)

Revision

- The responsible partner revises the draft based on feedback and resubmits for final approval at least 1 week before the deadline.
- The responsible partner fills the review template: [evolve2care_deliverable_internal_review_template.docx](#)

Submission

- PC submits the final version to the EC after final approval.

In particular, the deliverable deadlines for submission procedures are presented below:

Table 2 EVOLVE2CARE's Deliverables' submission procedure

Deliverable submission procedure	
Deadline	30 th or 31 st of the month
Table of contents	1.5 month prior to final submission
Ready-for-Review Version	15 th of the month
Review	15 th to 22 nd of the month
Version ready for submission	27 th of the month
Review by the Coordinator	Until the 30 th of the month
Submission to the EC	30 th or 31 st of the month

As outlined in Part A of the DoA, documents must be reviewed for **style, completeness, presentation, and alignment with deliverable objectives**. Additionally, they should be assessed for technical accuracy, soundness, and novelty (when applicable), as well as the completeness of results and their comparison with existing work, among other criteria.

Figure 8 EVOLVE2CARE deliverable template - snapshot

10. Project Leadership and Roles

10.2.Roles

Project Coordinator (PC) (Dr. Evdokimos Konstantinidis, AUTH, [linkedin.com/in/evdokimosk](https://www.linkedin.com/in/evdokimosk))

The role of the Project Coordinator (PC) is to represent the project and consortium, report to the Commission, and oversee overall project performance. They manage project resources, enhance visibility, and ensure effective communication with the Commission and stakeholders. Additionally, the PC chairs Project Steering Board meetings and handles formal project communications.

Scientific co-ordinator (SC) (Prof. Panagiotis Bamidis, AUTH, [linkedin.com/in/panagiotis-bamidis-4281354](https://www.linkedin.com/in/panagiotis-bamidis-4281354))

The role of the Scientific Coordinator is to audit the performance of Joint Research Activities and ensure the accomplishment of the project's scientific objectives.

Project Mission Coordinator (PMC) (Despoina Petsani, AUTH, [linkedin.com/in/despoina-petsani](https://www.linkedin.com/in/despoina-petsani))

The role of the Project Mission Coordinator is to ensure that the project's goals, vision, and objectives are clearly defined and effectively executed. They track progress and facilitate communication on a daily basis to keep the project on course.

Innovation Manager (IM) (Adriane Thrash, AV, [linkedin.com/in/adriane-thrash-60876323](https://www.linkedin.com/in/adriane-thrash-60876323))

The Innovation Manager is responsible for driving and overseeing the development of new ideas within the project while ensuring the successful and impactful implementation of the Open Call mini-consortia projects.

10.3.Publication Review Board

The **Publication Review Board (PRB)** will consists of the Project Coordinator (PC), Scientific Coordinator (SC), Project Mission Coordinator (PMC), and Innovation Manager (IM). Its role is to oversee publications and ensure they meet the highest scientific and quality standards.

10.4. External Expert Advisory Board

The EEAB (External Expert Advisory Board) will support and guide the Consortium in decision-making.

To provide valuable insights into the project's development, the EEAB will meet every six months (3 times throughout the project duration) with the Consortium. They will review the project's progress and offer constructive feedback.

The EEAB will include C-level experts in healthcare, pharma, living labs, startups, EIT programs, regulatory matters, and research. The board will be finalized within the first six months of the project by the Consortium.

10.4.3. Members

EVOLVE2CARE project has already contacted and confirmed the participation of the following members in the EEAB.

Table 3 EVOLVE2CARE Advisory Board

Member	Sector
Costas Piliounis	Healthcare/Pharma (short CV pending)
Maika Sabido Siller Project Manager at Basque Health Cluster	Maika holds a degree in Analytical Chemistry and a master's in Quality and Environmental Management. She has extensive experience in clean room micro/nanoelectronics technology processes, as well as in development, manufacturing, and regulatory affairs for a class III medical device company. She is currently part of Basque Health Cluster, as project manager.
Katerina Zisaki Quality Assurance Management Systems & Regulatory Affairs Director PKNM Solutions Sàrl	Katerina demonstrates a multidisciplinary profile into the Quality and Regulatory Sector. Working and Participating into quality undertakings for more than 10 years from different roles, she has possessed her responsibilities into Quality Assurance

	<p>and Regulatory Affairs through Management and Consulting roles for the design, development, implementation, verification and validation and clinical evaluation as well as auditing of medical, IVDs and medicinal products. Katerina is a QMS auditor and technical expert in the filed of medical devices for two EU Notified Bodies, while she contributes as Consultant to the IVD Prequalification team of WHO.</p>
--	---

10.5. Ethics Advisory Board

The Ethics Advisory Board will be responsible for attending Board meetings and providing guidance to the Evolve2Care consortium on ethics issues identified by the Project Coordinator. The Board's expertise will ensure that the project's approach to regulatory challenges in HealthTech innovation within the Transitional Care sector aligns with ethical standards. The Board will review key regulatory barriers and enablers, particularly in relation to Living Lab services supporting innovators. To support their work, all necessary documents will be provided in advance, enabling informed discussions and recommendations on ethical considerations affecting researchers, startups, and the implementation of the funded mini-consortia. Preparatory work for each meeting will not exceed one hour.

The Ethics Advisory Board will consist of at least 50% external advisors identified by the consortium partners, who will receive formal invitations to participate. The consortium will also evaluate whether a Non-Disclosure Agreement needs to be signed between the external advisors and the consortium. The role is voluntary and no monetary compensation is expected for the Board.

10.6. External Ethics Advisor

The Independent Ethics Advisor (IEA) will be responsible for reviewing the Ethics section of short-listed project applications, which includes an Ethics Self-Assessment questionnaire, descriptions of ethical considerations/issues, and the proposed methods for addressing them. The IEA will provide a written opinion on the ethics issues identified in the projects and assess how these issues are addressed by the

applicants. If necessary, the IEA may request additional information from applicants if the provided details are insufficient or if ethical issues are not clearly outlined. Only projects that pass the ethics evaluation process will be eligible for funding.

Selection process

Given the importance of the External Advisor a specific selection process has been created:

- Suggestions for the Advisors position are shared by all partners.
- The Consortium reviews the resumes and selects the person with the best fit.
- The Potential advisor is invited to join.
- If the selected candidate refuses to participate, the consortium moves to the next best fit.

11. Performance metrics (KPIs)

The performance metrics (KPIs) of EVOLVE2CARE and the partners responsible for them, as agreed during the project kick-off meeting are presented in the following table:

Table 4 EVOLVE2CARE's KPIs and responsible partners

KPI Number	Description	Target Goal	Responsible Partner
1.1	Training Programs increasing knowledge on experimentation frameworks	2	ENoLL/AV
1.2	Living Labs participating in trainings	20	ENoLL
1.3	Living Labs engaged in user centric knowledge and experimentation activities	40	ENoLL
1.4	Services for testing innovations	10	ENoLL/Harmonization WG
1.5	Action Plans	1	AUTH
2.1	Innovations tested	10	Sploro/AUTH
2.2	Countries covered	20	Sploro
2.3	Organizations to inform	20	Sploro

2.4	Stakeholders researched	>50	Sploro/VILABS
3.1	Supervisory authorities reached	5	VILABS
3.2	Countries covered	20	VILABS
3.3	Areas identified	3 Uses Cases	AUTH
3.4	Experimentation spaces	1 centralized (AccelUp) covering multiples experimentation spaces i.e., LLs	AUTH/ENoLL
3.5	Regulators reached	10	VILABS/AV
4.1	KICs/projects/ EU initiatives reached	7	AUTH/ENoLL
4.2	Living Labs reached	100	ENoLL
4.3	Multipliers reached	20	AUTH
4.4	RTOs reached	20	VILABS/AUTH
4.5	Knowledge sharing workshops	2	VILABS

More details can be found in the corresponding Excel: [Evolve2Care_KPIs.xlsx](#)

12. Conclusions

This deliverable describes the operational and managerial procedures of EVOLVE2CARE focusing on the core processes that will take place during the project's duration. More specifically, this handbook provides essential guidelines for managing the EVOLVE2CARE project, covering project meetings, management tools, document handling, dissemination, and scientific publications. It ensures compliance with data protection, quality assurance, and financial reporting. By defining roles, responsibilities, and performance metrics, it promotes effective collaboration and accountability, supporting the successful execution of the project and its goals.

This deliverable is a living document and the Coordinator (AUTH) is responsible for updating it reflecting any potential changes. This document serves as a reference point for any management activities of the project.

Annex 1 Data Management Plan

EVOLVE**2**CARE

D5.1 – Data Management Plan (DMP)

WP5 – Project Coordination and Management

January 2025 | Version 1.0

Funded by
the European Union

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Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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1.1	23-01-2025	Gaburici David [SPLORO]	Second Draft
2.0	24-01-2025	Panos Kartsidis [AUTH]	Review and final changes

List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifiers
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan sets out how the project partners will monitor data processing both during the implementation phase and after the project has been completed. It covers key aspects essential for properly managing data and includes a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP). DMP describes the lifecycle of the project data, and the activities related to its processing and protection. This includes information on the collection, storage, access, sharing, protection, retention, and eventual destruction of data, including personal data. Each project partner involved in handling and managing data collected, stored, or used as part of the project has contributed detailed information on their data management practices, all of which are included in this document.

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1. Introduction

Innovative research projects such as EVOLVE2CARE, funded by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon Europe programme, involve extensive data processing, often including sensitive information. To ensure compliance with legal and ethical standards, these projects require a Data Management Plan (DMP). The DMP outlines how data is generated, shared, used, and stored, following the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" to balance transparency and security. This approach ensures sound data governance while maintaining research integrity.

In addition to meeting regulatory requirements, effective data management improves data quality, accessibility, and organization, supports efficient research, and enables the reuse and validation of studies. The DMP serves as a dynamic document that will evolve over the course of the project, providing a comprehensive overview of the datasets, the rules for handling the data, and the importance of proper management to promote excellence in research and data sharing for future endeavours.

1.1. Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE is a transformative initiative that aims to accelerate HealthTech innovation in transitional care by addressing barriers to development, adoption, and commercialization. By leveraging a network of certified Living Labs across Europe, the project enables real-world experimentation to uncover and tackle challenges such as interoperability, ethical considerations, and regulatory hurdles that cannot be fully addressed with traditional testing environments. Through the AccelUP platform, EVOLVE2CARE brings together innovators, regulators, and stakeholders and provides a coordinated marketplace for testing and improving HealthTech solutions. This user-centric approach fosters collaboration, ensures regulatory compliance, and aligns innovation with real patient and market needs. The project focuses on critical areas of transitional care, including hospital discharge management, home care monitoring, and elderly care transitions, and aims to improve the continuity and quality of care while accelerating the time to market for cutting-edge technologies.

Intending to foster knowledge sharing, EVOLVE2CARE standardizes the framework for experimentation and offers training programs to strengthen the capabilities of living labs and innovators. The initiative identifies and mitigates legal, regulatory, financial, and operational barriers to innovation while promoting best practices and collaboration across the healthcare ecosystem. By piloting at least 10 innovations and

integrating the lessons learned into actionable strategies, the project ensures that the solutions are both impactful and commercially viable. Ultimately, EVOLVE2CARE aims to create a sustainable environment for HealthTech innovation, streamline the transition from development to deployment, and support regulatory advances for personalized healthcare systems.

1.2. Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The DMP for the EVOLVE2CARE project covers the entire lifecycle of research data, from planning to publication and beyond. It outlines processes such as research design, data collection, processing, analysis, publication, dissemination, preservation, and reuse. By adhering to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and DMP guidelines, the project ensures compliance with data protection and privacy requirements while effectively managing data generation, access, curation, and storage.

The DMP serves as a formal self-regulatory instrument with a transversal character that guides the handling of data both during and after the project. It reflects the consortium's commitment to ethical standards, Horizon Europe guidelines, and principles of research integrity such as reliability, honesty, respect and accountability. By adhering to these standards, the project ensures the safety and dignity of the individuals whose data is processed, promoting trust and ethical compliance in all research activities.

This document is a key regulatory tool for data processing and data protection and serves as both a supplementary and stand-alone regulatory source. It applies to all project work packages and research activities where data and personal data are processed and sets out specific measures to ensure proper processing and protection. Given the different categories of data processed in this research, the DMP is essential to comply with legal and ethical requirements and to carry out the core project activities. It complements the project management and associated work packages. In addition, all dissemination activities in the publication of datasets must comply with the DMP rules and principles. Any methods, tools, or technologies developed for data processing must adhere to the principles defined in the DMP. Thus, the DMP underpins the ethical standards for all research and support activities within the project.

1.3. Structure

This DMP consists of seven chapters. The introduction is followed by an overview of data processing and summary of data planned to be processed within the project. The third provides both a conceptual point of view on FAIR principles and concrete plans how to meet these principles in the context of this project. The facts related to the personal data protection implemented in the project is given in chapter four. The following chapter is a section that outlines the DMP governance within this project. The overview of the security strategies and tactics used to secure the data within the project implementation are provided in the chapter six. At the very end, this DMP is rounded off with brief conclusions.

Annex 1 of this document contains the DMP Questionnaire that project partners that process data within this project have answered, whereas Annex 2 includes the answers.

1.4. Data processing – overview

The process of data processing in the context of project implementation involves various activities and several different contexts. Data is collected to gather stakeholder feedback on the barriers and drivers they face in developing innovation and to get their feedback on user requirements for the Accelup platform. Various details on the personal experiences of innovators, researchers, and living labs will be collected to be translated into user requirements for the Accelup platform. These activities will generate new data that will subsequently be analyzed for the further course of the project implementation. The data will also be processed in connection with the organization of open calls for the project pilots. The implementation of the pilot projects requires the selection of the most suitable project proposals for the implementation of the pilot projects. The selection of the most suitable project proposals includes an administrative review, a scientific evaluation, and an ethics evaluation. Ethics evaluation should be conducted by an external and independent ethics expert. In all these phases, certain data (including personal data) must be collected, exchanged between the project partners, and analyzed.

Figure 1 – Data processing lifecycle

The data will also be processed in the context of networking and dissemination of information about the project. On the one hand, some of the partners will disseminate the project activities in their own networks and living labs. Therefore, in addition to the project partners, other selected institutions will also have access to or receive information about the project activities. However, the dissemination and exploitation activities also include the dissemination of information to a wide audience through specific means (project website and social media). The data is also processed as part of internal project management, which includes (among other things) quality assurance through peer review of project deliverables. Finally, the analysis, use, and reuse of data is required for the development of scientific publications.

1.5. Data summary

The data summary provides an overview of the DMP aspects, focusing on data creation and data reuse. It addresses the reuse of existing data, data types and formats, the purpose of data processing and the relationship to the project objectives, the expected volume of data, data provenance, and the utility of the data. The section should serve as a basis for understanding the role of data in achieving the project's outcomes.

The EVOLVE2CARE project aims to leverage both newly generated and existing data to achieve its objectives of improving healthcare practices and outcomes. The project will re-use existing data from various sources, including:

- Publicly available datasets from prior health-related projects and literature, ensuring compliance with working package objectives from the grant agreement.
- ENOLL's existing databases of active members and participants in the Health & Wellbeing Working Group for disseminating questionnaires, open calls, and project information.
- Publicly available data on investors in the healthtech sector, which will be used by Anthology Ventures.
- Data from conference proceedings with citations of project outputs and audiovisual content from third-party organizers of events, used by VIL for reporting purposes and online content.

The rationale for re-using this data is to build on existing knowledge, ensure compliance, and maximize the project's impact. In addition to re-using existing data, EVOLVE2CARE will generate new data through various methods, including:

- **Surveys:** Quantitative data will be collected through surveys distributed to innovators, policymakers, EU initiative representatives, and other stakeholders. Survey data will provide insights into stakeholder needs, barriers and drivers of innovation, user requirements for the AccelUP platform, and the effectiveness of interventions.
- **Open calls:** Data from open call submissions, including application details, proposal documents, and evaluation scores, will be used to identify and support Living Labs participating in the experimentation phase.
- **Focus groups:** Qualitative data from focus group discussions will be used to gain insights into user experiences and barriers to healthcare.

- **Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews with innovators, policymakers, and EU initiative representatives will provide qualitative insights into stakeholder perspectives and experiences.
- **Project activities:** Aggregated data generated from pilot studies, surveys, and interviews will contribute to statistical analysis and reporting.

The project will utilize various data formats, including:

- **Structured data:** CSV and Excel formats for storing survey responses, open call application data, metadata on participant demographics, and other statistical data.
- **Text data:** DOCX, PPT, PDF, and TXT formats for storing training materials, focus group minutes, interview transcripts, and project reports.
- **Multimedia data:** MP4 and AVI formats for storing training videos and recorded webinars².
- **Machine-readable formats:** JSON and XML for storing metadata.
- **Image formats:** PNG and JPEG for storing graphs and visual representations of data.

The **expected size of the data** varies depending on the data source:

- SPLOROTECH SL estimates a total size between 10 and 100 MB for its datasets.
- ENOLL anticipates 1 GB each for contracts with open call winners and the ecosystem database and 10 GB for MOOC data.
- AUTH estimates less than 10 MB for its datasets.

The data generated and re-used in the EVOLVE2CARE project will be useful to a wide range of stakeholders, including:

- **Healthcare innovators:** Researchers, SMEs, startups, and technology providers can use the data to design and implement innovative solutions, improve interoperability, and address user needs.
- **Policymakers and regulatory bodies:** The data can inform policy development and regulatory decision-making related to healthcare systems and digital frameworks.
- **EU-funded initiatives and collaborations:** The data can foster alignment and collaboration among EU-funded projects and initiatives.
- **Healthcare providers and organizations:** Data insights can be used to optimize care delivery models and integrate digital health solutions.

- **Academic and research institutions:** The data can support research, publications, and future studies in healthcare innovation and interoperability.
- **Technology developers and standards bodies:** Data can be used to refine technical solutions, improve compatibility, and advance standards for interoperable systems.
- **General public and patient advocacy groups:** The data can help understand the impact of healthcare interventions and shape user-centered policies.
- **Data analysts and statisticians:** The data can be used for analysis, trend identification, and modeling.
- **Funding and investment bodies:** Data insights can be used to evaluate the potential of innovations and prioritize funding.
- **Educational institutions and training programs:** Data can be used to develop case studies, course materials, and practical examples.

Overall, the EVOLVE2CARE project's approach to data generation and re-use is designed to be comprehensive and impactful, aiming to improve healthcare practices, foster innovation, and benefit a wide range of stakeholders.

2. FAIR Principles

The FAIR principles outlined in the EC guidelines are fundamental to effective research data management in today's era of rapidly growing data volume and complexity. These principles — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable — were established to address the challenges of managing extensive datasets while ensuring usability and integrity across diverse research fields.

2.1. Findable Data

Enhancing the discoverability of data is vital for its effective use. EVOLVE2CARE partners focus on creating metadata and implementing robust identification mechanisms to improve data discoverability. This ensures that valuable research outcomes are easily accessible to relevant stakeholders. Public data intended for broad dissemination is shared through designated communication channels to promote transparency and knowledge exchange. Meanwhile, confidential data requiring strict access controls is safeguarded and shared only with authorized entities, adhering to data protection regulations. Project partners should address key questions regarding the data they handle:

- What is the name and nature of the data?
- Where is the data stored?
- How can the data be located?
- What standards are applied to facilitate its discoverability?

Given the diversity of project outputs, data may be presented for internal and external audiences. Publicly accessible data can be made available on project websites or other open platforms, while confidential data should be stored in secure repositories with access restricted to authorized entities.

Internal project documentation and associated data should be managed through a centralized repository system, such as a shared online platform. The repository owner (the project coordinator) oversees access rights, ensuring that only those who require specific data can access it. All files, folders, and datasets should be described in a common language (e.g., English) to maintain consistency and facilitate understanding.

The following practices are planned to enhance data findability and usability:

- Development and implementation of rich metadata for discovery:

- SPLOROTECH SL will create rich metadata for all datasets to ensure discoverability and compliance with FAIR principles. Metadata will include general information (title, description, keywords), access and licensing details, dataset-specific metadata (format, size, coverage), provenance and quality information, and relationships to other datasets. Metadata will be stored in a standardized format and made publicly available in relevant repositories.
 - ENOLL will create metadata for three types of data: contracts with open call winners, the ecosystem database, and MOOC data. Metadata will include details like Living Lab names, locations, thematic focus, stakeholders, initiative names, geographic scope, and learner demographics.
 - Anthology Ventures will create metadata for publications that include processed anonymized data.
 - VIL will not create metadata but will present aggregated data in detailed public reports.
- Use of search keywords:
 - SPLOROTECH SL will provide search keywords to optimize reuse possibilities.
 - ENOLL will provide search keywords.
 - Anthology Ventures will provide search keywords to optimize reuse.
 - VIL will provide search keywords to optimize reuse.

In addition, all the project partners are encouraged to implement the following measures:

- Organized storage: Documents should be stored in structured folders using standard formats (e.g., PDFs, Word documents, spreadsheets). Each partner is responsible for organizing their work in appropriate locations.
- Task identification: Files and folders should include task identifiers (e.g., T3.2) to link them to specific project activities.
- File naming: Names should include a concise title, author, and creation or revision date to ensure unique identification and traceability.
- Search functionality: The repository should support search features to enable users to locate files efficiently.

To ensure external entities can locate and access relevant data, the following provisions are stipulated:

- Public dissemination: Public deliverables and outputs should be published on project websites or deposited in institutional or other agreed-upon repositories.
- Digital object identifiers (DOIs): Assigning DOIs to datasets should ensure persistent citation and facilitates linking datasets to publications.
- Data sharing updates: Project partners should be informed about the availability, status changes, and location of datasets to streamline access and promote collaborative use of the data.

By adopting these measures, the project ensures that data remains accessible, discoverable, and aligned with best practices in research data management.

2.2. Accessible Data

Access to project data depends on factors such as data type, security measures, and organizational protocols. The project partners will manage and process various datasets, each with specific characteristics that influence decisions regarding access. To effectively address data access, each partner handling datasets for project purposes should consider the following key questions:

- Which data will be accessible, to whom, and for what purpose?
- When will the data be accessible?
- Which data will remain restricted and why?

Data access may range from being open to the general public to being limited to specific entities, depending on the type of data and the technical and organizational measures in place. These measures are designed to ensure data security, protect personal information, and safeguard project objectives. Publicly accessible data may be shared as part of the project's dissemination activities, while sensitive datasets may be restricted to select partners or stakeholders.

In some cases, anonymized datasets may be made available upon request to third parties for research purposes, provided such access aligns with the project's goals and complies with applicable security and data protection standards. The project evaluators may also be granted controlled access to data to fulfill evaluation requirements without compromising the confidentiality, security, or integrity of the data. Ultimately, data access will be governed by the purpose, scope, and nature of the data, as well as the measures implemented to ensure its protection and appropriate use.

To promote transparency and maximize the impact of research, project participants are encouraged to share their scientific results through open access. Beneficiaries must adhere to relevant agreements and policies, ensuring compliance with open access requirements for peer-reviewed publications. Thus, appropriate measures will be implemented to facilitate free online access to scientific outputs, ensuring that the research community and the public benefit from the project's findings.

In line with open data principles, beneficiaries must manage and share digital research data according to established requirements by the GA and EC rules. Data should be deposited in research data repositories, enabling third parties to access, analyze, and utilize the data at no cost. While promoting open access, beneficiaries must also ensure that data security, confidentiality, and personal data protection are upheld. In cases where unrestricted access to specific datasets might compromise the project's objectives, appropriate justifications should be documented. By balancing openness with protection measures, the project ensures responsible data sharing and knowledge dissemination.

Concerning the use of repositories for data storage the current plan can be summarized as follows:

- SPLORO will deposit applicant data in servers managed by Amazon Web Services (AWS) located in Germany and Ireland.
- ENOLL will use an Evolve2Care SharePoint system managed by AUTH.
- VIL will use a project repository for internal monitoring and a Zenodo community for publicly available deliverables and reports.
- Anthology Ventures will use organizational repositories, Zenodo, and the project drive.

As explained, the project consortium plans to make most of the data openly available. However, some datasets will be confidential or shared under restricted access conditions. The reasons for restricting data sharing could be categorized as follows:

- **Privacy and confidentiality concerns:** Datasets containing personal data or sensitive personal data, such as health-related information will be restricted due to requirements of data protection laws. For example, MOOC data includes personal learner data and must remain private. Additionally, the dataset managed by AUTH contains personal data and contact information and cannot be shared publicly.
- **Proprietary or commercial data:** Data collected from innovators, such as SMEs, startups, and corporates, might include proprietary or confidential

business information, such as intellectual property, trade secrets, or research that is in the process of patenting. Project partners will restrict sharing data from contracts with Open Call winners and the ecosystem database because the data includes sensitive information about participating organizations and individuals and may include proprietary or sensitive data.

- **Legal and ethical restrictions:** Certain legal and ethical requirements might prevent data sharing. For instance, informed consent obtained from participants in surveys or interviews might have explicit clauses restricting data sharing. In addition, contractual requirements such as those laid down by GA and imposed by EC rules can prevent access to data temporarily or permanently to certain stakeholders.
- **Data quality or incompleteness:** Datasets that are incomplete, poorly structured, or of low quality might be restricted until they meet the standards for public sharing.
- **Security concerns:** Datasets might be restricted if they contain sensitive research or project details to protect the integrity or security of the project or systems where data is stored. VIL will restrict data related to the project's monitoring efforts.

During the course of the project implementation public data will be accessible through the project website and reputable, publicly accessible research data repositories (e.g., Zenodo). Data will be accessible through standard tools for accessing spreadsheets, text, PDFs, and video files. Management of restricted data will be carried out by using the following mechanisms:

- **Formal controlling conditions** such as data use agreements, non-disclosure agreements, and data processing agreements.
- **“Need to know” access granting policy:** access to data will be limited to authorized personnel employed/engaged by the project partners whose nature and scope of work require access to data.
- **Identity verification:** the identity of a person accessing data will be ascertained through mandatory registration and approval through secure login systems.

2.3. Interoperable Data

Interoperability ensures seamless data sharing and integration within the research ecosystem. Data generated within this project will prioritize interoperability to ensure

seamless exchange, integration, and reuse across various entities and stakeholders. These include, but are not limited to, researchers, institutions, and organizations operating at national and international levels.

To enable effective data sharing and combination with other datasets, all project data will adhere to commonly accepted standards and formats. The data will be produced in formats that are compatible with widely used tools and capable of being processed by both proprietary and open-source software. Information exchange among project partners will employ suitable methods based on specific needs, including secure digital platforms, shared repositories, and local storage systems. Consistent use of standardized file formats will ensure accessibility and ease of integration, regardless of the software used. Even when data originates from proprietary tools, it will remain accessible via open-source alternatives where possible.

This approach to data interoperability aims to support lawful and legitimate data sharing and enable cross-dataset reusability, fostering broader collaboration, transparency, and innovation within the research and stakeholder community.

The project consortium will implement several concrete ways to ensure data interoperability. The use of metadata and standards for their development will impact data interoperability. Thus, the project will implement the following standards:

- Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) - provides a standardized vocabulary for Metadata description and will be used for basic metadata creation.
- Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) - used for documenting datasets in the social sciences, particularly suitable for EVOLVE2CARE's survey data and qualitative information¹.
- ISO 19115 (Geospatial Metadata) - ensures proper description of any geospatial data collected or processed during the project.
- OpenAIRE Guidelines - guarantee that data is openly accessible and compliant with EU Open Science policies.
- European Data Portal and EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) - ensure project data is deposited in compliant repositories and accessible for the broader research community.
- VIVO Vocabulary for Research Data (VIVO) - describes the relationship between project participants and their data contributions, aligning the data with the broader research ecosystem.

2.4. Reusable Data

To support knowledge transfer and broader utilization, the data generated in this project will be made reusable in accordance with applicable regulations regarding intellectual property management and rights (IPR). Reuse of data will be permitted, ensuring compliance with relevant legal and ethical frameworks, and the data will be made available for reuse as early as possible.

For the reuse of existing data and materials—such as figures, tables, quotations, and other relevant content sourced from academic publications, policies, reports, or press articles — proper referencing and citation practices will be strictly followed. Any necessary permissions for reuse will also be obtained to ensure compliance with legal and ethical standards.

Public deliverables and outputs will be made openly accessible through dedicated dissemination platforms, institutional repositories, or other suitable open-access channels. Users will have the right to share, redistribute, adapt, and build upon the materials for various purposes, including commercial use, provided they:

- Attribute the original source appropriately, including a clear indication of any modifications.
- Avoid applying legal or technological restrictions that limit others' lawful use of the materials.

Ownership of project results, including intellectual property rights, will be managed in line with agreed project governance frameworks and legal provisions. Dedicated project bodies will review and address any intellectual property concerns as needed. Updates to the DMP, including changes to ownership arrangements or IPR considerations, will be incorporated over the course of the project to reflect the latest developments.

As indicated, most data will be freely available through open repositories, project websites, and Zenodo. Majority of data will have an open-source format. Immediately available data includes open datasets to facilitate real-time collaboration. Also, data quality will be assured by a project data management team that will conduct manual reviews of key datasets before they are shared. Automated tools will also be used to validate metadata against standards. It is worth emphasizing that data processed by ENOLL will be licensed using Creative Commons licenses, including CC-BY-NC and CC-BY-NC-ND.

Figure 2 – FAIR principles

Adhering to the FAIR principles reflects a commitment to robust data management practices and fosters a culture of transparency, collaboration, and innovation within EVOLVE2CARE. By following these principles, project partners ensure that research data remains a valuable and accessible asset, driving scientific advancements and generating societal benefits. Moreover, compliance with the GA provisions concerning intellectual property rights and project ownership ensures accountability and integrity in data management, protecting the interests of all stakeholders involved.

Specific actions and details taken by project partners to fulfill these principles are detailed in their responses, which are provided in Annex 2 of this document.

3. Personal Data Protection and DMP

Strong privacy protection is rooted in effective data governance, which involves guiding privacy functions toward compliance with laws and regulations. This begins with defining the scope of personal data collection and processing, including

details such as the type of data, purpose of processing, storage location, transfer mechanisms, retention period, and security measures. Additionally, organizations involved in the project must identify applicable privacy laws and tailor legal requirements to their specific context. A well-scoped privacy program allows for a comprehensive understanding of the personal data lifecycle and associated legal, cultural, and operational challenges. A widely recognized framework for privacy governance is "Privacy by Design". This approach integrates privacy and data protection into every stage of the technology lifecycle, from design to disposal.

The key elements of personal data protection include adherence to the general data protection principles outlined in the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ensuring the fulfilment of data subject rights, and implementing effective technical and organizational measures.

3.1. Personal Data Protection Principles

The processing of personal data in the context of the project must be based on the principles of the General Data Protection Regulation and European data protection law. The processing of personal data must be lawful, fair, and transparent. To ensure the personal data processing is lawful the processing must comply with applicable laws, including data protection and other relevant regulations. To ensure lawful processing under the GDPR, one of six legal grounds must be met:

- Consent,
- Performance of a contract,
- Legal obligation,
- Vital interests,
- Public interest, or
- Legitimate interests.

If the processing is based on consent, this must be informed, freely given, specific, and unambiguous. Before processing, the data subjects should be clearly and comprehensibly informed about the scope, purpose, and consequences of the data

processing. If consent is obtained, this must be documented. This not only confirms the legal basis but also provides an accurate record of the processing activities. For other legal bases, controllers or processors must ensure that the chosen basis is appropriate. For example, if the controller relies on legitimate interests, it must ensure that these do not override the rights and freedoms of data subjects with regard to the protection of personal data.

Individuals should be informed about how their data is collected, used, or processed, including the scope and purpose of the processing. Transparency requires that information about the processing is easily accessible, understandable, and written in plain language. Important details such as the identity of the controller (the entity that determines the purpose and means of processing personal data) and the purpose of the processing must be provided, along with information to ensure fair and transparent processing. Individuals should be aware of the risks, rules, safeguards, and rights in relation to their data and how they can exercise these rights. Moreover, relevant project partners or their appointed Data Protection Officers must be capable to explain and answer questions about the processing of personal data.

Data should be processed for specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes determined at the time of collection. It must be adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary. Data retention should be kept to a minimum and processing should only take place if the purpose cannot reasonably be achieved otherwise. Personal data may be retained for an even longer period if this is required by law or is necessary for reasons of public interest, scientific or historical, and statistical purposes. In these cases, the data should be properly secured and the application of appropriate technical and organizational measures should ensure that only the necessary information is disclosed. Thus, controllers must set time limits for erasure or regular review of data to avoid unnecessary storage. Inaccurate data must be rectified or erased without delay. Finally, data must be handled securely to prevent unauthorized access or misuse; this includes securing the equipment used for processing.

Accountability is one of the cornerstones of the lawful and ethical processing of personal data. It implies the form of responsibility that requires organizations that process personal data to be able to demonstrate compliance with all the principles and obligations enshrined in the GDPR at all times. To this end, the organization must take concrete measures after conducting a risk analysis and must implement concrete measures, which it should also be able to demonstrate. In order to effectively comply with the relevant legal and ethics frameworks (e.g. the GDPR), it is therefore necessary

to ensure that internal rules (policies, standards, procedures, etc.) are adopted and enforced.

3.2. Data Subject Rights

Under the GDPR, individuals whose personal data is processed (data subjects) have several rights concerning the processing:

- Right of access: the right to request access to their personal data.
- Right to rectification: the right to request corrections to inaccuracies and to ensure the accuracy of the data.
- Right to erasure: request the deletion of their personal data.
- Right to restrict or object to processing: to limit or object to further processing.
- Right to data portability: request to receive a copy of their personal data in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format upon request.
- Right to withdraw consent: if the processing is based on consent, the data subject can withdraw this at any time and thus prevent further processing. However, this does not affect the lawfulness of any previous processing.
- Right to lodge complaints: Filing a complaint with a data protection supervisory authority.

If personal data is reused, information about further processing must be provided to inform the data subjects and, when required, obtain their consent, in particular for the reuse of their data. Data subjects always have the option of withdrawing their consent, opting out of further communications, and requesting deletion of their data from the project records. In cases where secondary personal data is used, public sources, approved sources for research purposes or engagement activities are carefully checked for compliance and appropriateness.

It should be emphasized that the exercise of data protection rights is not unconditional. There are conditions set out in the GDPR as to when, how, and under what circumstances data protection rights can be exercised. Due to contractual obligations and compliance with mandatory laws, including the EU regulations, the project partners may be forced to reject certain requests from data subjects (e.g. requests to delete data) in order to comply with the regulations/obligations with legal precedence.

3.3. Accountability

The principle of accountability is a cornerstone of data protection regulations such as GDPR. It requires organizations to take responsibility for and demonstrate compliance with data protection principles. The accountability principle requires entities that process personal data to implement robust governance measures, including clear policies, secure processing practices and comprehensive record keeping. Accountability extends beyond mere compliance; it involves a proactive and ongoing commitment to the protection of personal data throughout its lifecycle. This ensures transparency and trust between stakeholders, including data subjects, regulators and project partners.

In the context of this project, the principle of accountability underpins the DMP by assigning direct responsibility to each project partner for their respective data processing and data protection practices. Each partner must adhere to the project's data protection rules, including those enshrined in the GA, and follow the specific rules regarding data retention periods. To ensure compliance, each project partner has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) or designated a person responsible for data protection in their organization (contact information can be found in section C of the DMP questionnaire). These individuals oversee data protection activities, provide guidance on data protection compliance and serve as a point of contact for all data protection-related inquiries. By adhering to these shared responsibilities and ensuring compliance at individual and consortium level, the project ensures a consistent approach to the protection of personal data while meeting its legal and ethical obligations.

3.4. DMP Governance

The process of developing the DMP began before the start of project activities. The project proposal was subjected to an ethical evaluation through the process of the Ethics Appraisal Schema. During this process, the ethics evaluators assessed the ethical aspects of various areas, including the processing of personal data. The project proposal received a conditional ethics clearance, which led to the obligation **to fulfil ethics requirements related to the third-party funding of technology experiments potentially involving, the participation of humans in project activities, the protection of personal data, the environment, health and safety, and artificial intelligence (AI)**. The project consortium must form an ethics committee, consisting of at least one external and independent ethics expert with

expertise in the fields of third-party funded projects. Therefore, this committee is planned to review and offer a written opinion on short-listed proposals for funding with regard to any potential issue regarding (among other things) personal data protection/processing.

Concerning the participation of humans in the project, it will include stakeholders and experts from relevant domains. The inclusion/exclusion criteria for the participation of experts and stakeholders will rely on their capabilities to generate appropriate feedback that might contribute to the project's ambitions and objectives. Their selection will be based on the relevance of knowledge and experience considering required parameters and expected outcomes. Participation of experts will be only on a voluntary basis. The project will not include persons unable to provide consent, children, or vulnerable groups. Participation is consent-based and where necessary, a project information sheet and consent forms will be provided stating facts about the project and ensuring the respect and exercise of individuals' rights.

The lawfulness of processing personal data will rely on the participants' informed, freely given, specific, and unambiguous consent. Personal data processing within EVOLVE2CARE will refer to the stakeholders' and experts' contact details and opinions. Personal data processing will comply with all relevant EU and national data protection laws as well as applicable ethical standards. All relevant rules will be applied in order to process data in a lawful and fair manner, to provide all necessary info to data subjects, to minimize the scope of data that will be processed, to ensure data processing is carried out only for agreed research purposes, and to preserve accuracy, integrity, and confidentiality of data. In addition, we will ensure fairness, transparency, and accountability regarding the data processing.

In order to protect the environment and health and to ensure the safe implementation of the project activities, the project consortium will undertake to comply with the applicable international, EU, and national laws. The project partners will take all necessary precautions based on plausible scientific evidence of serious risks. The project partners employ experienced researchers in the field who are able to fully assess safety concerns and/or their willingness to tolerate risks. This will ensure that the technology and methods do not have adverse environmental or health impacts and do not compromise safety. Where required, the necessary approvals will be obtained/confirmed.

The AI will be strictly developed under the applicable EU regulatory framework on the development of AI, taking into account particularly the EU AI Act and European Commission Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.

Finally, the project consortium will develop necessary self-regulation that will contribute to the relevant regulatory landscape and regulate procedures and concrete steps that all project partners should adhere to ensure the project objectives and activities are ethically compliant. All the taken measures will be provided in the deliverable within an additional work package (WP6) that set up to deal with the ethics requirements.

3.5. DMP Governance – technical development

By signing the GA, the project beneficiaries (project partners) agreed to comply with several contractual obligations related to data processing activities. These commitments serve to operationalize the FAIR principles, which are embedded in the rules for the implementation of projects granted by the EC. The DMP is an integral part of D5.1 and it will be structured in two iterations. Whereas the first, the current one (developed in the early stage of the project implementation) has the form of the general plan, the second one (planned to be submitted in the later stage of the project implementation) will provide more specific details, including info about the implementation of the initial DMP plan and realized actions.

The development of the first iteration of the DPM started with the workshop organized to inform all the project partners about the notion and importance of DMP. Also, the workshop was used to present operational details regarding the development of the DMP. As a follow-up, a detailed questionnaire was prepared and distributed to all project partners. All project partners have contributed to the development of the first iteration of the DMP by providing information about the data they have collected in the questionnaire. By completing the questionnaire, they have provided details of their own data processing activities.

3.6. DMP Questionnaire

The DMP questionnaire is divided into five sections and is used to gather information for the initial DMP iteration. The template for this questionnaire can be found in Annex 1 of this document.

Section A focuses on summarizing data. Its purpose is to collect detailed information about how data is collected or generated within the project. It aims to clarify the relationship between the data and the project's objectives, the types and formats of data involved, potential sources, and the data management and privacy protection methods employed. By addressing these aspects (purpose, types, formats, origins, uses, and methods) the questionnaire ensures alignment with project goals, ethical standards, and privacy regulations. This section serves to collect information valuable to reveal details related to transparency, accountability, and informed decision-making concerning data-related processes.

Section B ensures compliance with FAIR data principles, essential for fostering data sharing, collaboration, and reuse within the scientific communities, general audience, and other project stakeholders. This section evaluates aspects like data discoverability, accessibility, and interoperability of data to improve its quality, transparency, and reproducibility, thereby enhancing the impact of research outputs. Taking into account that researchers and project partners are encouraged to consider broader implications and adopt best practices for data sharing and management, this section is divided into four subsections:

- B1: Making data findable – Examines metadata creation and the discoverability of project data.
- B2: Making data openly accessible – Assesses data accessibility, restrictions, repositories, and access control mechanisms.
- B3: Making data interoperable – Focuses on file formats used for storing and sharing data.
- B4: Increasing data reuse – Considers the potential for third-party use of project-generated data.

Section C gathers information on personal data processing within the project, ensuring GDPR compliance. It emphasizes transparency and risk mitigation related to handling personal data. This section identifies the types of personal data processed, the purposes of processing, and the relevance of the data to project goals. It also inquires about special categories of data under Article 9 of the GDPR, which require additional safeguards. Furthermore, it addresses data-sharing and transfer practices, ensuring alignment with GDPR requirements and minimizing risks associated with personal data processing.

Section D focuses on data storage and retention within the organizations involved in the project. It examines where datasets are or will be stored, assessing security

measures, compliance, and potential risks associated with storage solutions (e.g., cloud or on-site servers). The section also addresses data deletion procedures, including methods for secure deletion or anonymization when data is no longer needed. These practices are critical for regulatory compliance, such as meeting GDPR's right to erasure requirements, and for minimizing retention-related risks. By gathering this information, the questionnaire supports data security, privacy, and compliance while identifying areas for improvement in storage, access, and deletion practices. Finally, this section contains contact details of the project partners' DPOs or personal in charge of personal data protection.

Section E, the final part of the questionnaire, provides space for additional information about adherence to other national, funder, sectorial, or departmental data management procedures.

This comprehensive approach ensures thorough documentation and adherence to best practices in data management, security, and compliance across all aspects of the project.

4. Data security

EVOLVE2CARE is a collaborative research project involving a consortium of various partners. While there is no unified information security standard that all partners must follow, each partner should implement robust information security management practices to ensure the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of data. These practices are tailored to uphold the highest levels of security and compliance throughout the project.

To begin with, project partners are encouraged to establish comprehensive information security policies. These policies should clearly define the security strategy, procedures, and technical requirements, and they must be communicated to all stakeholders to foster a unified or at least harmonized understanding of security protocols. To strengthen the security framework, partners should integrate information security into a structured management system. This includes clearly assigning roles and responsibilities for information security within teams, implementing risk management processes to identify and mitigate potential threats, and ensuring that all team members are well-informed about security guidelines and their respective responsibilities.

For effective asset management, including the handling of collected or generated data, assets used for data processing must be appropriately classified and assigned to responsible owners. This ensures that data and other assets are adequately protected throughout their lifecycle. Data will be transferred using encrypted channels, such as HTTPS, FTPS or VPNs, to prevent unauthorized interception. Access control measures should be rigorously enforced, granting access only when necessary and revoking it promptly when no longer required. Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) will be used to control who can view, edit or share data. Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) will be used to access repositories and cloud storage to provide additional layers of security. Regular security audits should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of these controls.

Cryptography is one of the critical components of securing sensitive data. Partners are expected to use effective cryptographic techniques, informed by current recommendations and risk assessments, to safeguard data integrity and confidentiality. Additionally, physical and environmental security measures should be implemented to prevent unauthorized access to facilities and resources. These measures should be designed to protect both the research processes and the data

managed by the project partners. To support this, dedicated teams should oversee security measures, monitor incidents continuously, and respond promptly to any security breaches. A clear incident management process must be established and enforced to handle such events effectively.

With regard to data retention, unnecessary data will be erased after completion of processing activities. Data will be permanently erased from all storage systems, following the industry's best practices, involving secure wiping to ensure data cannot be recovered. Necessary data will be retained for an additional 5 years after the project's completion, following EC rules. Anonymized or open data will be kept indefinitely.

All partners are also committed to ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and standards. By aligning research activities and operations with applicable legal and regulatory requirements, the consortium minimizes the risk of non-compliance and maintains trust in the project.

This strategic and tactical approach to data security aligns with the highest security standards. Details of the specific security measures implemented by each partner can be found in Section C of the answers (Annex 2) provided by the project partners.

5. Conclusion

Data processing within research projects like EVOLVE2CARE presents certain legal and ethical challenges. While sharing data in the public domain offers significant societal benefits, the risks associated with inappropriate data disclosure require careful management. Achieving the right balance between openness and data protection is essential. Following the FAIR data management principle, data should be "as open as possible, as closed as necessary." Consequently, the project must adhere to all relevant national and international regulations governing data processing.

This document serves as a critical resource for data processing and protection. The Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a framework for self-regulation, combining general standards and principles with actionable measures to which all project partners are committed. These obligations and measures are grounded in both legal and ethical considerations, derived not only from national and international laws but also from project-specific regulations, such as EC requirements.

The DMP governs data management throughout the project lifecycle, covering all datasets processed during the project and extending to data use after project completion. As the project generates a variety of outputs, including multiple data categories, the DMP leverages appropriate resources to maintain high data quality. The DMP serves a dual purpose: ensuring that data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), and fostering the development of trustworthy data.

Finally, this document reflects the project partners' commitment to meeting regulatory requirements and conducting the project in line with the highest research standards. It stands as evidence of their dedication to balancing openness and data protection while maintaining ethical and legal integrity in all aspects of data management.

DMP Annex – DMP Questionnaire

DMP Questionnaire

This questionnaire should provide details necessary for the development of the Data Management Plan. The Data Management Plans (DMPs) is a key element of good data management. The DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by PROJECT-NAME project.

The methodology for the development of the DMP is based on the European Commission [Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020](#) and the best practices regarding personal data protection.

Before you start answering the questions, we recommend that you talk to the relevant stakeholders in your organization/institution about the questions and the details requested (e.g. the IT and security teams should be contacted to gather information about data security practices) and then answer the questions. Please note that you may be unable to provide many details about data processing at the beginning of the project implementation. Therefore, if the required details are not known at the beginning of the project implementation, the DMP will be updated later, and the details will be included in the following iterations of the DMP.

General Information	
Partner Name	
Corresponding person (email)	

A – Data Summary	
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? ⁱ <i>Please Specify</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect? ⁱⁱ <i>Please Specify</i>
3	Please list all the data sets that you process (or plan to process) during the project implementation. <i>Please Specify</i>
4	What is the purpose of processing each of the dataset(s) you listed above? <i>Please Specify</i>
5	Please list all the data attributes for each dataset you listed above and describe each of the attributes. <i>Please Specify</i>
6	What formats of data will you generate/collect? ⁱⁱⁱ <i>Please Specify</i>
7	Will you re-use any existing data and how? ^{iv} <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
8	What is the origin of the data? ^v <i>Please Specify</i>
9	What is the expected size of the data? ^{vi} <i>Please Specify</i>

10	Please explain to whom your datasets will be shared once your processing activities are complete.	Please Specify
11	To whom might the data be useful? ^{vii}	Please Specify
12	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data? ^{viii}	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data

B1 - Making data Findable

1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	Please Specify
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? ^{ix}	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	Please Specify
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? ^x	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

B2 - Making data openly accessible

1	Accessibility ^{xi}	<input type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why ^{xii}	Please Specify
3	How will the data be made accessible ^{xiii}	Please Specify
4	Which repository will be used? ^{xiv}	Please Specify
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Please Specify
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? ^{xv}	Please Specify
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Please Specify
10	Is there a need for a data access committee? ^{xvi}	Please Specify
11	Are there well-described conditions for access (e.g. a machine-readable license, etc.)?	Please Specify
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Please Specify

B3 - Making data interoperable

1	File format Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
	2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	Please Specify	

B4 - Increase data re-use		
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? ^{xvii}	<i>Please Specify</i>
2	Data owner ^{xviii}	<i>Please Specify</i>
3	When will the data be made available for re-use? ^{xix}	<i>Please Specify</i>
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? ^{xx}	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? ^{xxi}	<i>Please Specify</i>

C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process? ^{xxii}	<i>Please Specify</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data? ^{xxiii}	<i>Please Specify</i>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<i>Please Specify</i>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR? ^{xxiv}	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data? ^{xxv}	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No
8	Please provide the contact details of your Data Protection Officer (DPO) or a person formally responsible for data protection matters on behalf of your organization.	<i>Please Specify</i>
9	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<i>Please Specify</i>

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<i>Please Specify</i>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data) ^{xxvi}	<i>Please Specify</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<i>Please Specify</i>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<i>Please Specify</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? ^{xxvii}	<i>Please Specify</i>

- I State the purpose of the data collection/generation.
 - ii Define the nature of the data, e.g. quantitative, qualitative, numeric, text, audio, structured, unstructured, etc.
 - iii Define the format of the data, e.g. txt, xlsx, doc, pdf, etc.
 - iv Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any).
 - v Specify the origin of the data.
 - vi State the expected size of the data (if known).
 - vii Outline the data utility, to whom will it be useful, e.g. research groups, private sector, citizens, etc.
 - viii Define if privacy preservation techniques are required before making your data open.
 - ix Define the metadata standards you use. Link regarding the metadata standards:
<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/list>.
 - x Outline the approach towards search keyword (e.g. search keywords will be provided when the dataset will be uploaded to the repository).
 - xi Will data produced and/or used in the project be made openly available?
 - xii If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.
 - xiii Specify how the data will be made available, e.g. by deposition in a repository.
 - xiv Specify which repository will you use, e.g. Zenodo, open-access journal, project website, etc.
 - xv E.g. Zenodo, open-access journal, project website, etc.
 - xvi Specify why.
 - xvii License conditions: Copyright, Creative Commons, Open License, etc. A list of licenses can be found here
<https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>
 - xviii List the data owner, the copyright owner, the intellectual property owner.
 - xix E.g. Immediately, after the end of the project (specify the exact time), along with the publication of main results, etc. If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
 - xx If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.
 - xxi Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable, e.g. 5 years after the conclusion of the project.
 - xxii E.g. email addresses, phone numbers, affiliation, position, research notes, interviews
 - xxiii E.g. for contacting project partners, for conduct interviews necessary for research purposes
 - xxiv Special categories of data are personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation
 - xxv If yes, you should collect evidence that previous beneficiary has lawfully processed the data and applied appropriate technical and organizational measures for securing data.
 - xvi Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.
 - xxvii Indicate if you must adhere to other policies and procedures for data management.
-

DMP Annex 2 – Project partners’ answers

AUTH

General Information	
Partner Name	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Corresponding person (email)	Despoina Petsani (dpetsani@auth.gr)

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Data will be collected in order to: 1) Gather stakeholders feedback on the barriers and drivers that they face for the development of innovations (T1.1) 2) Gather stakeholders feedback on user requirements for the Accelup platform (T1.2) 3) Experience of innovators, researchers and Living Labs that will participate in the EVOLVE2CARE open calls, aiming to translate that in user requirements for the Accelup platform (T3.1) 4) Facilitate the Open-calls' administrative obligations
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	We will collect mainly two types of data: 1) Quantitative through questionnaires 2) Qualitative through interviews and focus groups 3) Direct identifiers (contact information) 4) Demographics
3	Please list all the data sets that you process (or plan to process) during the project implementation.	Two datasets will be produced: 1) Demographics and contact information of the participants in the Open Calls 2) Qualitative and quantitative feedback from project stakeholders regarding the need for innovation in transitional care and user requirements for the Accelup platform
4	What is the purpose of processing each of the dataset(s) you listed above?	1) Request follow-up information and correlate population demographics with the produced feedback 2) Update user requirements for the Accelup platform
5	Please list all the data attributes for each dataset you listed above and describe each of the attributes.	Dataset 1 name, surname, ID/Passport Number, sex, age, affiliation, email, telephone number, full address, Dataset 2 TBD
6	What formats of data will you generate/collect?	Mainly csv and word format
7	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify):
8	What is the origin of the data?	The participants and stakeholders will provide the data
T	What is the expected size of the data?	<10MB
10	Please explain to whom your datasets will be shared once your processing activities are complete.	N/A
11	To whom might the data be useful?	<i>The data will be useful to the Evolve2Care consortium. The two datasets will be analysed to create insights that will be shared with the relevant stakeholders of the project.</i>
12	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (The data processing practice will adhere to the data minimization principle by collecting and subsequently processing the scope of data that is strictly needed for the purpose of processing and not beyond it. Data aggregation will be performed during the analysis of a dataset and anonymization will be performed at a later date with the intent of distribution.):

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data				
B1 - Making data Findable				
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			
2	What metadata will be created? No			
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): N/A			
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how N/A			
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			
B2 - Making data openly accessible				
1	Accessibility <input type="checkbox"/> Public data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential data			
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why Dataset 1 (Personal data and contact information) cannot and will not be made publicly accessible nor shared with anyone not having a legal basis of processing. Dataset 2 will not be shared for disclosing it will infringe the IPR of the consortium.			
3	How will the data be made accessible <i>The data will not be public accessible.</i>			
4	Which repository will be used? <i>The data will not be public accessible.</i>			
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? <i>The data will not be public accessible.</i>			
opinions6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):			
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? N/A			
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided? N/A			
10	Is there a need for a data access committee? N/A			
11	Are there well-described conditions for access (e.g. a machine-readable license, etc.)? N/A			
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? N/A			
B3 - Making data interoperable				
1	File format Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
	2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow? N/A		
B4 - Increase data re-use				
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? N/A			
2	Data owner AUTH			
3	When will the data be made available for re-use? N/A			

4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	N/A

C - Personal Data		
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions		
1	What types of personal data will you process?	1) Demographics like date of birth, country and city of residence, address, sex, employment status, working position, interviews, opinions 2) Contact information like email and phone 3) VAT number
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	1) Demographics will be used in order to finetune the user requirements for certain population (e.g., younger vs older users) 2) Contact information will be maintained for the duration of the study period in order to contact participants for any project related issues (e.g., reimbursements, feedback collection, interviews)
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	Dataset will consist of direct identifiers, contact information and demographics, which will facilitate the administrative processing of the Open Call's applications. The collected data is the minimum required to fulfil the obligations of the consortium to (at a minimum) administer payments/reimbursements, arrange visits, provide access, evaluate the outcomes of the Open Calls and collect feedback as described in the GA. Dataset 2 will not include personal data.
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Within the consortium, when required by the GA, with the consent of the data owners. Data will be securely transferred via encrypted and password protected means (e.g., MS sharepoint). <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Please provide the contact details of your Data Protection Officer (DPO) or a person formally responsible for data protection matters on behalf of your organization.	Mrs Kornilia Vikelidou data.protection@auth.gr
9	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	The datasets will be stored in the private SharePoint folder of the project.
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	Strict user access policies have been implemented using Microsoft's user management and access settings. Access has been granted only to authorised members of the project. SharePoint allows for granular permissions to control who can view, edit, or share data using RBAC (Role-Based Access Control). Our team periodically reviews and updates user access rights based on internal changes within the project's members. Sharepoint provides all the functionalities regarding data security, such as log files of changes, versioning, data recovery and more.
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	N/A

4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	The access to the data will be limited to the members of the Evolve2Care consortium. Access to data will require secure login and identification, while any processing is logged.
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

SPLORO

General Information	
Partner Name	SPLOROTECH SL
Corresponding person (email)	miguel.garcia@sploro.eu

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>The purpose of data collection is to evaluate, monitor, and optimize the EVOLVE2CARE project outcomes. This involves gathering insights to support the development of evidence-based interventions aimed at improving healthcare practices and outcomes in line with the project's objectives.</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	<p><i>The data generated will include:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Quantitative data (e.g., survey responses, numerical health metrics)</i> <i>Qualitative data (e.g., interviews, focus group minutes)</i> <i>Metadata describing collected datasets</i> <i>Descriptive statistics and aggregate summaries</i>
3	Please list all the data sets that you process (or plan to process) during the project implementation.	<p><i>List of datasets</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Survey responses from Innovators (researchers, SMEs, startups, corporates), Policy makers / Regulatory bodies, EU initiatives (e.g., EIT Health projects)</i> <i>Data from open calls</i> <i>Focus group minutes.</i> <i>Data from the interviews from Innovators (researchers, SMEs, startups, corporates), Policy makers / Regulatory bodies, EU initiatives (e.g., EIT Health projects)</i> <i>Metadata on participant demographics and geographic distribution.</i> <i>Other statistical Data</i>
4	What is the purpose of processing each of the dataset(s) you listed above?	<p><i>To understand stakeholder needs and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions.</i></p> <p><i>To gain qualitative insights into user experiences and barriers to health care.</i></p> <p><i>To test the feasibility and impact of the proposed solutions.</i></p>
5	Please list all the data attributes for each dataset you listed above and describe each of the attributes.	<p>Survey Responses</p> <p><i>Attributes:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Participant Type: Indicates the group (e.g., Innovator, Policy Maker, EU Initiative representative).</i> <i>Participant ID: Unique anonymized identifier for each respondent.</i> <i>Timestamp: Date and time the response was submitted.</i> <i>Demographics: Age, gender, organization type, and location.</i> <i>Survey Questions: Text of each question in the survey.</i> <i>Responses: Answers provided by participants (multiple-choice, scaled ratings, open-ended text).</i> <i>Other</i>

	<p>Data from Open Calls</p> <p>Attributes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Project ID: Unique identifier for each open call submission.</i> • <i>Organization Type: Classification of the submitting entity (e.g., SME, Startup, Researcher, Other).</i> • <i>Submission Date: Date of application.</i> • <i>Proposal Title: Name of the proposed project.</i> • <i>Summary: Brief description of the project proposal.</i> • <i>Funding Requested: Amount requested by the applicant.</i> • <i>Evaluation Score: Assigned score from reviewers.</i> • <i>Status: Outcome of the application (e.g., Accepted, Rejected).</i> • <i>Other</i> <p>Additional:</p> <p><i>Applicants' data collected in this project will be managed with "Accelerator App" (by Splorotech, S.L.). For each proposal a random code of about 65 characters (composed by numbers and letters) will be generated (by a standard algorithm), so each proposal will be identified by a unique identifier. This identifier is a not repetitive code.</i></p> <p><i>Data processed in this project focuses on data collected from the applicants, evaluators and mentors themselves. The processing of these data does not require the generation of associated metadata.</i></p> <p><i>Regarding the generation of metadata, the Sploro's platform (https://cascadefunding.sploro.eu/application/new?program=women-techeu-call-for-evaluators) generate a time stamp associated with each applicant proposal, so that the precise moment in which that proposal was sent can be proven.</i></p> <p><i>Regarding the generation of secondary data (those that have not been provided directly by applicants), the project's websites can generate statistic information (such as Country, OS...). This analytic information does not include personal data (nor the IP of the user).</i></p> <p>Focus Group Minutes</p> <p>Attributes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Discussion Topics: Key themes and questions addressed.</i> • <i>Feedback Points: Summarized contributions or opinions of participants.</i> • <i>Action Items: Tasks or follow-ups identified during the session.</i> • <i>Other</i> <p>Interview Data</p> <p>Attributes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Interviewee ID: Unique anonymized identifier for each interview participant.</i> • <i>Participant Type: Classification (e.g., Innovator, Policy Maker, EU Initiative representative).</i> • <i>Interview Date: Date when the interview was conducted.</i> • <i>Questions Asked: List of structured or semi-structured questions.</i> • <i>Responses: Detailed textual answers.</i> • <i>Themes: Key insights or recurring ideas extracted during analysis.</i> • <i>Other</i> <p>Metadata on Participant Demographics and Geographic Distribution</p> <p>Attributes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participant ID: Corresponding anonymized ID for consistency across datasets.</i> • <i>Age Group: Age range of participants (e.g., 18–25, 26–35).</i> • <i>Gender: Gender identity (optional, self-reported).</i> • <i>Role: Participant's professional role (e.g., Researcher, Startup Founder, Policymaker).</i> • <i>Organization Type: Type of organization represented by the participant.</i> • <i>Country/Region: Geographic location (e.g., EU member state, non-EU country, Associated Country).</i> • <i>Other</i> <p>Other Statistical Data</p>
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		<p>Attributes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Metric Name:</i> Specific parameter measured (e.g., rates, engagement levels). • <i>Value:</i> Numerical value of the metric. • <i>Time Period:</i> Date range or time frame for the data point. • <i>Source:</i> Dataset or method used to calculate the statistic. • <i>Aggregation Level:</i> Level of data grouping (e.g., individual, organization, regional). • <i>Other</i>
6	What formats of data will you generate/collect?	<p>Survey Responses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>CSV/Excel:</i> For structured survey data (e.g., participant responses). <p>Data from Open Calls</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>CSV/Excel:</i> For application data and evaluation scores. • <i>PDF:</i> For submitted project proposals and supporting documents. <p>Focus Group Minutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>TXT/Word (DOCX):</i> For textual meeting summaries and minutes. <p>Interview Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>TXT/Word (DOCX):</i> For transcription of interview responses. • <i>PDF:</i> For summarized interview reports. <p>Metadata on Participant Demographics and Geographic Distribution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>CSV/Excel:</i> For structured metadata (e.g., demographic attributes). • <i>JSON/XML:</i> For metadata storage in machine-readable formats. <p>Other Statistical Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>CSV/Excel:</i> For aggregated statistics and data visualizations. • <i>PNG/JPEG:</i> For graphs and visual representations of data. • <i>PDF:</i> For reports containing analyzed data and statistical summaries.
7	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We will re-use publicly available datasets from prior health-related projects and literature, ensuring compliance with working packages objectives from grant agreement.
8	What is the origin of the data?	<p>The origin of the data for the EVOLVE2CARE project will include the following sources:</p> <p>1. Survey Responses <i>Primary Source:</i> Data will be collected directly from stakeholders via structured online surveys distributed to: <i>Innovators (e.g., researchers, SMEs, startups, corporates).</i> <i>Policy makers and regulatory bodies.</i> <i>Representatives of EU initiatives (e.g., EIT Health projects).</i></p> <p>2. Data from Open Calls <i>Primary Source:</i> Open call submissions will be collected directly through the project's dedicated application portal. <i>Secondary Source:</i> Some elements may be derived from pre-existing public databases or similar calls if applicable.</p> <p>3. Focus Group Minutes <i>Primary Source:</i> Collected from live discussions conducted with partners.</p> <p>4. Interview Data <i>Primary Source:</i> Derived from semi-structured interviews with innovators, policy makers, and representatives of EU initiatives, conducted by the project team.</p> <p>5. Metadata on Participant Demographics and Geographic Distribution <i>Derived from Surveys and Interviews:</i> Participant demographics and locations will be recorded during survey and interview processes. <i>Secondary Source:</i> Publicly available demographic and regional data may complement this dataset.</p> <p>6. Other Statistical Data <i>Derived from Project Activities:</i> Aggregated data will be generated from pilot studies, surveys, and interviews. <i>Secondary Source:</i> Comparative statistical data may be derived from publicly available reports, databases, or prior EU-funded initiatives for benchmarking.</p>
9	What is the expected size of the data?	<p>The expected size of the data for the EVOLVE2CARE project can be estimated based on the types and sources of data being collected:</p> <p>1. Survey Responses</p>

		<p>Approximately 1–5 MB per survey dataset, depending on the number of responses. Estimated size: ~10–50 MB for all surveys.</p> <p>2. Data from Open Calls Text-based application data: ~1–2 MB per dataset. Proposal documents (PDFs): ~1–10 MB per file. Estimated size: ~50–100 MB, depending on the number of submissions.</p> <p>3. Focus Group Minutes Text: ~1–5 MB per session. Estimated size: ~15–25 MB, depending on the number of sessions.</p> <p>4. Interview Data Notes: ~1–5 MB per interview. Estimated size: ~15–50 MB, depending on the number of interviews.</p> <p>5. Metadata on Participant Demographics and Geographic Distribution Tabular metadata (CSV/JSON): ~1–5 MB. Estimated size: ~5–10 MB.</p> <p>6. Other Statistical Data Aggregated data in CSV/Excel format: ~1–5 MB. Visualizations (charts, graphs): ~1–10 MB per dataset. Estimated size: ~5–20 MB.</p>
10	<p>Please explain to whom your datasets will be shared once your processing activities are complete.</p>	<p>1. Project Consortium Partners Purpose: For internal analysis, reporting, and further development of project outcomes. Access Level: Full access to all datasets, including sensitive data, under strict confidentiality agreements.</p> <p>2. European Commission (EC) Purpose: To fulfill reporting obligations and demonstrate the project's results and impact. Access Level: Aggregated and anonymized data, as well as raw data upon request, in compliance with Horizon Europe guidelines.</p> <p>3. Academic and Research Institutions Purpose: To facilitate further research and collaboration in healthcare innovation and digital interoperability. Access Level: Anonymized datasets and statistical summaries.</p> <p>4. Policymakers and Regulatory Bodies Purpose: To support policy development and regulatory decision-making related to healthcare systems and digital frameworks. Access Level: Aggregated and anonymized data relevant to policymaking.form</p> <p>5. Public and External Stakeholders Purpose: To enhance transparency, promote public understanding of the project outcomes, and support re-use in aligned initiatives. Access Level: Open access to anonymized and aggregated datasets through repositories such as Zenodo or the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).</p> <p>6. Specific Data Users (upon approval) Potential Users: Innovators, SMEs, startups, and other organizations involved in healthcare innovation. Access Level: Restricted datasets may be shared under non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) to ensure ethical and legal compliance.</p> <p>7. Journal and Conference Publications Purpose: To disseminate results through academic publications and presentations. Access Level: Only summarized, aggregated, or anonymized data will be included. All data sharing will adhere to ethical standards, data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR), and the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).</p>
11	<p>To whom might the data be useful?</p>	<p>The datasets generated by the EVOLVE2CARE project may be useful to the following stakeholders:</p> <p>1. Healthcare Innovators Who: Researchers, SMEs, startups, corporates, and technology providers in the healthcare domain. Purpose: To design and implement innovative healthcare solutions, improve interoperability of digital systems, and address user needs based on the data insights.</p> <p>2. Policymakers and Regulatory Bodies Who: National and EU-level policymakers, regulatory authorities, and standardization bodies.</p>

		<p><i>Purpose: To develop evidence-based policies, regulations, and guidelines that promote interoperability, data security, and innovation in healthcare systems.</i></p> <p>3. EU-Funded Initiatives and Collaborations <i>Who: Projects and initiatives under Horizon Europe, EIT Health, and other EU programs.</i> <i>Purpose: To use the data as a foundation for collaborative efforts and to enhance alignment with broader EU goals in healthcare and digital transformation.</i></p> <p>4. Healthcare Providers and Organizations <i>Who: Hospitals, clinics, and other care providers.</i> <i>Purpose: To better understand patient needs, optimize care delivery models, and integrate digital health solutions into practice.</i></p> <p>5. Academic and Research Institutions <i>Who: Universities, research centers, and think tanks focused on healthcare, technology, and digital ecosystems.</i> <i>Purpose: To analyze the data for academic research, publish findings, and inform future studies in healthcare innovation and interoperability.</i></p> <p>6. Technology Developers and Standards Bodies <i>Who: Developers of eHealth platforms, digital wallets, and standards organizations.</i> <i>Purpose: To refine technical solutions, improve system compatibility, and advance standards for eIDAS-compliant wallets and other interoperable systems.</i></p> <p>7. General Public and Patient Advocacy Groups <i>Who: Citizen groups and organizations advocating for patient rights and improved care.</i> <i>Purpose: To understand the impact of healthcare interventions and contribute to shaping user-centered healthcare policies.</i></p> <p>8. Data Analysts and Statisticians <i>Who: Professionals working in health data analysis and visualization.</i> <i>Purpose: To derive insights, identify trends, and create models based on the project's aggregated and anonymized data.</i></p> <p>9. Funding and Investment Bodies <i>Who: Investors, venture capitalists, and funding organizations.</i> <i>Purpose: To evaluate the potential of healthcare innovations informed by the data and prioritize funding for impactful solutions.</i></p> <p>10. Educational Institutions and Training Programs <i>Who: Training organizations, universities, and educational platforms.</i> <i>Purpose: To develop case studies, course materials, and practical examples for teaching healthcare innovation and interoperability. By serving a diverse set of stakeholders, the project's data can drive innovation, inform policies, and improve healthcare delivery across multiple domains.</i></p>
<p>12</p>	<p>Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Yes, data aggregation, minimization, and anonymization methods will be applied to the data collected and processed during the EVOLVE2CARE project to ensure compliance with ethical standards, privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR), and the FAIR principles. Here's how these methods will be implemented:</p> <p>1. Data Aggregation <i>Purpose: To combine individual data points into summaries or group-level information, minimizing the identification of specific individuals or entities.</i> <i>Application: Aggregated data will be used for statistical analysis, reporting, and decision-making.</i> <i>For example, survey and interview responses results will be summarized into trends or patterns, rather than retaining individual responses. This ensures that personal or sensitive data is not directly exposed while still enabling meaningful insights.</i></p> <p>2. Data Minimization <i>Purpose: To collect only the minimum amount of data necessary to achieve the project's objectives and to limit the exposure of sensitive information.</i> <i>Application: During surveys, interviews, and data collection, only essential data will be collected (e.g., demographic information necessary for analysis). Non-essential or sensitive data (such as detailed personal identifiers) will be excluded.</i> <i>For instance, participant names will not be collected in raw form; only anonymized identifiers will be used.</i></p> <p>3. Anonymization</p>

		<p>Purpose: To prevent the identification of individuals from the data, ensuring privacy and confidentiality.</p> <p>Application: Personally identifiable information (PII) such as names, email addresses, and phone numbers will be removed or replaced with anonymized identifiers.</p> <p>In datasets such as survey responses and interviews, identifying information will be masked or coded before sharing. Additionally, any sensitive details that could lead to identification (e.g., very specific job roles or locations) will be generalized or aggregated. Special attention will be paid to participant demographics and geographic distribution to ensure no re-identification is possible. These methods will be applied in all phases of data processing to ensure that the privacy of individuals is respected and that the data remains suitable for research and analysis in a responsible and ethical manner.</p>
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B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data

B1 - Making data Findable

1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	<p><i>The following metadata will be created for the datasets generated in the EVOLVE2CARE project:</i></p> <p>1. General Metadata for All Datasets</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Title: Descriptive title of the dataset (e.g., "Survey and Interviews Responses").</i> • <i>Description: A brief description of the dataset, including its purpose, scope, and content.</i> • <i>Keywords: Relevant search terms</i> • <i>Creator(s): Names of the researchers or project members responsible for the dataset collection or creation.</i> • <i>Publisher: The organization responsible for managing the dataset (e.g., the EVOLVE2CARE project or participating partner (e.g., Sploro).</i> • <i>Date of Creation: The date when the dataset was first generated.</i> • <i>Version: The version number of the dataset, particularly if multiple iterations exist over time.</i> • <i>Language: The language(s) of the dataset (e.g., English).</i> <p>2. Data Access and Licensing Metadata</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Access Restrictions: Any restrictions on access to the data (e.g., confidential or sensitive data, controlled access).</i> • <i>Data Access URL: A direct link to where the data can be accessed or downloaded (e.g., evolve2care website, survey lime link).</i> • <i>Data Use Conditions: Any conditions or limitations regarding the use of the dataset (e.g., attribution requirements, data sharing policies).</i> <p>3. Dataset-Specific Metadata</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Data Format: The format of the dataset (e.g., CSV, Excel, JSON, PDF).</i> • <i>Data Size: The size of the dataset (e.g., in MB or GB).</i> • <i>Geographic Coverage: The geographic region represented in the dataset (e.g., EU, global, specific countries).</i> • <i>Temporal Coverage: The time period covered by the data</i> • <i>Methodology: Brief description of how the data was collected (e.g., online surveys, interviews, focus groups between partners).</i> <p>4. Provenance and Quality Metadata</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Data Provenance: The origin of the data, including the sources and processes used to collect or generate it (e.g., references from the literature review)</i> • <i>Quality Assurance: Any measures taken to ensure the quality, validity, and reliability of the dataset (e.g., data cleaning, validation steps).</i> • <i>Data Validation: Information on how the data was checked for accuracy (e.g., cross-referencing with existing datasets).</i> <p>5. Relationships to Other Datasets</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Related Datasets: Links to other datasets that are related or complementary to the one in question (e.g., other datasets from Horizon Europe projects).</i> • <i>Data Interoperability: If the dataset is compatible with other systems or standards</i> <p><i>This metadata will be stored in a standardized format to ensure discoverability and compliance with the FAIR principles. It will be made publicly available in relevant repositories to facilitate reuse and transparency.</i></p>
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <i>In terms of metadata development, our research is cross-functional and encompasses several domains. We will use omnipresent and recognized metadata vocabularies as described in this document.</i> <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	More details are provided in the sub-section 2 of this section
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	<p><i>If certain datasets in the EVOLVE2CARE project cannot be shared or need to be shared under restrictions, it would be due to the following reasons:</i></p> <p>1. Privacy and Confidentiality Concerns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Sensitive Personal Data: If the datasets contain personally identifiable information (PII) or sensitive personal data (e.g., health-related information, demographic details) that could potentially identify individuals, sharing may be restricted due to privacy laws such as GDPR.</i> • <i>Data Minimization and Anonymization: While anonymization and data minimization techniques will be applied, some datasets might still include information that, even if anonymized, could be subject to restrictions due to the sensitivity of the content. For example, detailed geographical locations or specific medical conditions might be considered sensitive in certain contexts.</i> <p>2. Proprietary or Commercial Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Commercial Sensitivity: Some data collected from innovators (such as SMEs, startups, and corporates) may include proprietary or confidential business information, such as intellectual property, trade secrets, or research that is in the process of patenting. This data might be restricted to avoid intellectual property risks and ensure that the commercial interests of the involved parties are protected.</i> • <i>Data from Open Calls or Specific Agreements: Data collected through open calls, such as from collaborators or external partners, may be subject to contractual agreements that restrict its sharing to protect commercial interests or preserve the confidentiality of the partners involved.</i> <p>3. Legal and Ethical Restrictions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ethical Considerations: In some cases, the informed consent obtained from participants in surveys, or interviews may have explicit clauses restricting data sharing. For example, certain participants may not have consented to having their data shared publicly or made available to third parties.</i> • <i>Jurisdictional Legal Requirements: Legal restrictions related to specific jurisdictions (e.g., countries with more stringent data protection laws) may also prevent sharing. If the data was collected from participants in countries with strict data protection laws, there may be limitations on how the data can be shared, especially internationally.</i> <p>4. Data Quality or Incompleteness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Incomplete or Low-Quality Data: Some datasets may be incomplete, poorly structured, or of low quality, making them unsuitable for sharing. If the data cannot be cleaned or processed to a sufficient standard, it might be kept restricted until it meets the necessary standards for public sharing.</i>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Preliminary Data: Early-stage data or preliminary findings from ongoing research may also be restricted, as sharing such datasets could lead to misinterpretation or incorrect conclusions being drawn.</i> <p>5. Security Concerns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Sensitive Research or Project Details: Certain datasets could contain information that is part of ongoing research or is related to confidential aspects of the project, such as methodology, early results, or other sensitive project details. Sharing such datasets could compromise the integrity or security of the project.</i> <p>Solutions for Restricted Sharing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Restricted Access: Where sharing is not possible, datasets could be made available under controlled conditions. For instance, data could be shared with specific partners or stakeholders under a Data Use Agreement (DUA) or Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA).</i> • <i>Anonymization/Redaction: In some cases, we can provide anonymized or redacted versions of the datasets to minimize privacy risks while allowing broader access.</i> • <i>Data Access Committee: If there are significant restrictions, a data access committee might be formed to oversee and approve data sharing requests, ensuring that any release is done in compliance with legal and ethical standards.</i> <p><i>By outlining these restrictions, we aim to ensure the integrity, privacy, and legal compliance of the datasets, while still enabling appropriate access and reuse where possible.</i></p>
<p>3</p>	<p>How will the data be made accessible</p>	<p><i>The data collected in the EVOLVE2CARE project will be made accessible in a secure, organized, and transparent manner to ensure that it is available for reuse, in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). The following steps will be taken to ensure that the data is properly shared and made accessible:</i></p> <p>1. Data Repository for Public Access <i>Deposition in an Open Repository: The datasets will be deposited in reputable, publicly accessible research data repositories. (e.g., such as evolve2care website, Zolando)</i></p> <p>2. Metadata for Discoverability <i>Comprehensive Metadata: Each dataset will be accompanied by detailed metadata that includes descriptions of the data, keywords, licensing, access rights, and information on how the data can be reused. This metadata will ensure that the datasets are easily discoverable through search engines and repository platforms. Searchable Keywords: We will use appropriate keywords that enhance discoverability.</i></p> <p>3. Access Rights and Licenses <i>Access Restrictions: For datasets with restricted access (e.g., due to privacy, intellectual property, or legal reasons), we will apply the appropriate access controls, such as requiring users to request access or limiting data availability to specific groups. In these cases, access might be granted under Data Use Agreements (DUA) or Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA).</i></p> <p>4. Documentation and Supporting Materials <i>Dataset Documentation: Datasets will include documentation explaining the content, structure, methodology, and limitations of the data. This will help users understand the context and ensure they can correctly interpret the data. Software and Tools: Where applicable, we will include any necessary software tools, code, or scripts that are required to process or analyse the data. We will explore the option of sharing these tools in open-source format, to maximize the reuse of the data.</i></p> <p>5. Versioning and Updates <i>Dataset Versioning: Each dataset will be versioned to track changes over time. This will ensure that users can always access the most up-to-date version of the data, while previous versions remain accessible for reference. Regular Updates: If new datasets are generated during the project, they will be added to the repository and made accessible to users as they become available. Updates will be accompanied by version control to maintain a clear audit trail.</i></p>

		<p>6. Additional Data Access Mechanisms Data Access Committee (DAC): For highly sensitive data or datasets with restricted access, a Data Access Committee may be established to review and approve requests for data access, ensuring compliance with ethical, legal, and security requirements.</p> <p>Direct Access Links: If datasets are made available through specific project websites or platforms, direct access links will be provided for stakeholders to easily download or view the datasets.</p> <p>7. Long-Term Accessibility Archiving and Preservation: Data will be archived in the selected repository, ensuring long-term preservation and access beyond the project's lifecycle. The repository's infrastructure will guarantee that the data remains accessible to users well into the future, following appropriate digital preservation strategies. In summary, the data from the EVOLVE2CARE project will be made accessible through reputable open repositories, backed by comprehensive metadata, clear documentation, and appropriate licensing. We will ensure that access restrictions, if necessary, are in place while maintaining transparency and maximizing reuse.</p> <p>8. Applicants' data will be collected by using Accelerator App (by Splorotech, S.L.), so it will be deposited in servers managed by Splorotech, S.L. This hosting service is provided by "Amazon Web Services" (AWS) and the location of these servers is within EU territory (Germany and Ireland). Splorotech, S.L. has arrangements with the service provider (AWS), regulating the processing of data in accordance with European regulations.</p>
4	Which repository will be used?	Project website
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	<p>Software for Documentation Viewing: PDF readers (e.g., Adobe Acrobat Reader) or document editors (e.g., Microsoft Word, Google Docs) may be required for users to access any supplementary documentation explaining how to use or interpret the datasets.</p> <p>Digital Rights Management (DRM) or Data Access Agreements (DAA) might be needed in cases where datasets are shared under restricted conditions (e.g., due to privacy or commercial sensitivity). Tools that support secure access and compliance with data sharing agreements will be required.</p> <p>In conclusion, the methods or software tools required to access the EVOLVE2CARE datasets will depend on the type and format of the data. These tools will ensure that users can efficiently access, analyze, and use the datasets while maintaining security, privacy, and compliance with relevant regulations.</p>
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Project website
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	<p>If there are restrictions on the use of certain datasets in the EVOLVE2CARE project, access will be provided through a controlled, secure, and transparent process. The following methods will be employed to ensure that restricted data is accessible only to authorized users while still adhering to ethical, legal, and privacy guidelines:</p> <p>1. Data Access Requests Requesting Access: Users who wish to access restricted datasets will need to submit a formal data access request. This request can be submitted through a dedicated form or email, which will include: A clear description of the user's affiliation (e.g., researcher, policy maker). The specific dataset or data subset they wish to access. The intended purpose of using the data. Any relevant certifications or agreements (e.g., ethical clearance, GDPR compliance).</p> <p>2. Data Use Agreements (DUA) Legal Agreements: For sensitive data, such as personal data or proprietary information, a Data Use Agreement (DUA) will be required. The DUA will specify:</p>

		<p><i>Conditions for Use: The specific purposes for which the data can be used, such as academic research, policy analysis, or public health improvement.</i></p> <p><i>Confidentiality and Data Protection: Requirements for ensuring the confidentiality of the data and compliance with GDPR or other applicable data protection laws.</i></p> <p><i>Restricted Access: Guidelines on how the data must be stored, processed, and shared, including any restrictions on redistributing or publishing the data.</i></p> <p><i>Duration of Access: The period during which the user is allowed to access the data and any conditions for renewing or terminating access.</i></p> <p>3. Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA)</p> <p><i>For Highly Sensitive Data:</i></p> <p><i>In cases where data is considered highly sensitive (e.g., confidential industry data or personal health information), a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) may be required in addition to the DUA. This agreement will legally bind the user to maintain strict confidentiality and prevent unauthorized disclosure of the data.</i></p> <p>4. Access Control Mechanisms</p> <p><i>Restricted Access Links:</i></p> <p><i>For datasets with restrictions, access may be provided via a password-protected link, or the data may be hosted on a secure server or cloud platform that requires authentication (e.g., through institutional or project-based login credentials).</i></p> <p><i>Data Access Platforms:</i></p> <p><i>Some datasets may be stored in platforms that allow fine-grained access control, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) or other secure cloud repositories. These platforms will support:</i></p> <p><i>Role-based access control (RBAC) to restrict data access to specific roles or users.</i></p> <p><i>Temporary or time-limited access for users who need the data for a particular project or research purpose.</i></p> <p>5. Ethical and Compliance Reviews</p> <p><i>Ethical Approval:</i></p> <p><i>If the data involves sensitive personal or health-related information (e.g., survey data with identifiable participants), users may be required to obtain ethical approval from an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics committee before they can access the data.</i></p> <p><i>GDPR Compliance:</i></p> <p><i>For datasets that involve personal data of EU citizens, users will need to comply with GDPR guidelines, and a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) may be required. The access process will include ensuring that users understand their obligations under GDPR, including data minimization and safeguarding personal information.</i></p> <p>6. Data Access via a Data Access Committee (DAC)</p> <p><i>Oversight and Approval:</i></p> <p><i>If necessary, a Data Access Committee (DAC) will be established to review data access requests. The DAC will be responsible for:</i></p> <p><i>Ensuring that access requests are legitimate and comply with ethical, legal, and privacy requirements.</i></p> <p><i>Reviewing the purpose and intended use of the data.</i></p> <p><i>Deciding on whether to grant, deny, or conditionally approve access based on the project's guidelines.</i></p> <p>7. Secure Data Handling</p> <p><i>Secure Storage and Transfer:</i></p> <p><i>Users accessing restricted data will be required to follow best practices for data security. This includes:</i></p> <p><i>Using encrypted storage and secure file transfer protocols (e.g., SFTP, HTTPS) to prevent unauthorized access during the download or transfer of the data.</i></p> <p><i>Storing data in password-protected or encrypted files or on secure servers.</i></p> <p><i>Anonymization:</i></p> <p><i>If applicable, certain datasets may be anonymized or pseudonymized before being shared to reduce privacy risks. Access to raw or personally identifiable data may be limited to approved researchers with the appropriate legal and ethical clearance.</i></p> <p>8. Monitoring and Compliance</p> <p><i>Audit Trails:</i></p>
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10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No, only simple data will be collectible	
11	Are there well-described conditions for access (e.g. a machine-readable license, etc.)?	Yes	
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	The data will be available to public through the project website.	
B3 - Making data interoperable			
1	<p>File format</p> <p>Spreadsheet: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> CSV</p> <p>Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> HTML</p>	<p>Structured data: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> JSON</p> <p>Geographical data: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON</p>	<p>Image: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> PNG</p> <p>Video: <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ</p> <p>Other (please specify):</p>
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	<p>For the EVOLVE2CARE project, we will follow widely recognized data and metadata standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to ensure that the data is properly documented, discoverable, interoperable, and reusable. This will help in maintaining consistency, ensuring compliance with regulations, and facilitating the effective sharing of data within the project and with external stakeholders.</p> <p>Data and Metadata Standards to Follow: Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: DCMI is a widely used standard for describing metadata for resources, especially in the context of digital data. • Relevance: It provides a standardized vocabulary for metadata description, which can be adapted for the EVOLVE2CARE project to describe the datasets (e.g., dataset title, creator, date, and description). • Application: Dublin Core elements will be used for basic metadata creation to describe datasets and related resources, ensuring consistency and discoverability across the project's outputs. <p>Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: The DDI standard is widely used for documenting datasets in the social sciences, especially those involving surveys, interviews, and focus group data. • Relevance: Since EVOLVE2CARE collects survey data and qualitative information (e.g., focus group and interview transcripts), the DDI standard is an ideal choice for documenting these data. • Application: The DDI standard will be used to document variables, data collection methods, and data structure. This will 	

		<p>ensure that the survey responses and interview data are comprehensively described for later use or analysis.</p> <p>ISO 19115 (Geospatial Metadata)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Purpose: This is the international standard for geospatial metadata, used for documenting geographic or spatial data.</i> • <i>Relevance: If the project involves the collection or processing of geospatial data (e.g., geographic distribution of participants, mapping of EU initiatives, etc.), this standard will be used to ensure proper description of spatial data.</i> • <i>Application: The ISO 19115 standard will be used to describe geographic features and metadata for spatial datasets within the project.</i> <p>OpenAIRE Guidelines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Purpose: OpenAIRE provides guidelines for data management in European research projects, particularly regarding open access and data sharing.</i> • <i>Relevance: As part of a Horizon Europe project, the EVOLVE2CARE project must adhere to OpenAIRE guidelines for ensuring that data is openly accessible and compliant with EU Open Science policies.</i> • <i>Application: We will follow OpenAIRE guidelines to ensure datasets are stored in certified open repositories and to provide consistent metadata for dataset discovery and reuse.</i> <p>European Data Portal and EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Purpose: These frameworks promote the adoption of open data practices in Europe, with guidelines on data sharing, FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), and metadata standards.</i> • <i>Relevance: Following the principles of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) will ensure that project data is deposited in compliant repositories, accessible, and reusable for the broader research community.</i> • <i>Application: We will align our project’s metadata with the EOSC standards and guidelines to ensure the project’s data is interoperable across European research platforms.</i> <p>FAIR Data Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Purpose: These principles provide a framework for managing and sharing data to maximize its usefulness in the research community.</i> • <i>Relevance: Ensuring that data is FAIR is a core requirement of Horizon Europe projects. By adhering to FAIR principles, the project will enable better data discoverability, usability, and reusability.</i> • <i>Application: The project’s data will be made findable through metadata creation, accessible through open repositories, interoperable through standardized formats, and reusable by providing clear usage rights and documentation.</i> <p>VIVO Vocabulary for Research Data (VIVO)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Purpose: VIVO is a framework for describing research data, particularly research outputs, people, and organizations in the academic and scientific communities.</i> • <i>Relevance: It will be used to describe the relationship between project participants (e.g., researchers, SMEs, innovators) and their data contributions, aligning the data with the broader research ecosystem.</i> • <i>Application: VIVO will help describe participant roles and affiliations within the EVOLVE2CARE project and help in metadata generation, ensuring better integration of the project with research networks.</i> <p>Controlled Vocabularies for Research Domains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Purpose: Controlled vocabularies ensure uniformity and consistency when describing research topics, methodologies, and results.</i>
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Relevance: For the EVOLVE2CARE project, controlled vocabularies will be used to standardize terminology related to healthcare, innovation ecosystems, and policy-making.</i> • <i>Application: We will use vocabularies such as Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) or domain-specific thesauri to ensure consistent use of terms, improving data sharing, discovery, and analysis.</i> <p>Metadata and Vocabulary Methodologies: Metadata Creation and Description Methodology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Data Description: Metadata will be created for each dataset following the above standards to ensure that the datasets can be easily identified, understood, and reused. For example, survey responses and interview data will be described with information on data collection methods, instruments used (e.g., survey questionnaires), and metadata related to variables (e.g., response categories).</i> • <i>Data Provenance: Metadata will also include information about the data provenance (i.e., the origin of the data and its changes over time), ensuring that users know where the data came from and how it has evolved.</i> • <i>Versioning: As the project progresses, datasets may undergo multiple versions. Metadata will track changes between versions to ensure clarity on which dataset version is being shared or used.</i> <p>Data Interoperability and Standardization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The use of open standards for data and metadata (e.g., CSV for tabular data, JSON for web-based data exchange, XML for metadata) will ensure interoperability between systems, making it easier to share and integrate data across different platforms and disciplines.</i> • <i>Controlled Terminologies: We will use controlled vocabularies to ensure that terms related to healthcare innovations, policy-making, and research methods are standardized, improving the consistency and meaning of the data.</i> <p>Metadata Validation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Automated Tools: We will use automated tools to validate metadata against the standards (e.g., using XML Schema or JSON Schema validation for structured data formats) to ensure that metadata conforms to agreed-upon standards and includes all necessary fields.</i> • <i>Manual Review: A project data management team will also conduct manual reviews of key datasets to ensure high-quality metadata, adherence to standards, and completeness before data is shared with repositories.</i> <p>Data processed to manage the project Open Calls will be processed using Accelerator App (by Splorotech, S.L.). All the users must identify and authenticate themselves to access the platform. Access to the platform is parameterized so that users only access the necessary information based on their profile. More detailed information on this matter can be consulted in section 5 (“Data Security”) of this document.</p> <p>Conclusion: <i>The EVOLVE2CARE project will follow a combination of widely recognized data and metadata standards, including Dublin Core, DDI, ISO 19115, OpenAIRE, FAIR principles, and VIVO to ensure that the project’s data is well-documented, findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. By using these standards and methodologies, the project will improve data discoverability, foster collaborations, and contribute to the open science ecosystem.</i></p>
B4 - Increase data re-use		
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	Restrictive Licensing for Sensitive Data

		<p><i>In cases where data cannot be fully open due to legal or ethical concerns (e.g., GDPR compliance for personally identifiable information), specific measures will apply:</i></p> <p>1. Custom Data Usage Agreement (DUA) <i>Description: A tailored agreement specifying permissible use, data access restrictions, and obligations (e.g., confidentiality).</i> <i>Application: Pseudonymized or anonymized datasets requiring controlled access (e.g., focus group or interview data).</i></p> <p>2. No License (Confidential Data) <i>Description: Some datasets containing sensitive or proprietary information may remain confidential and not be licensed for reuse.</i> <i>Application: Raw data with personally identifiable information or commercially sensitive data.</i></p> <p>Public Repository Selection <i>Licensed datasets and metadata will be deposited in open repositories that support the chosen licenses, ensuring proper visibility and accessibility. Examples include:</i></p> <p><i>European Data Portal: Aligns with European Open Data principles.</i> <i>List of Licenses from Open Definition</i> <i>The licenses we plan to use are included in the Open Definition License list, ensuring compatibility with recognized open data standards:</i></p> <p><i>By adopting these licenses, the EVOLVE2CARE project ensures compliance with open science policies and maximizes the impact and reusability of its data.</i></p>
<p>2</p>	<p>Data owner</p>	<p><i>Data Ownership for EVOLVE2CARE Project</i> <i>Ownership of the data generated or collected during the EVOLVE2CARE project is distributed based on roles, contributions, and the nature of the data. Below is a detailed breakdown of data ownership:</i></p> <p>1. Data Owner <i>The primary data owner will be Splorotech SL (SPLORO), the legal entity responsible for coordinating and managing the data collection and processing activities in the project for his assigned target groups as TG#1: Innovators, TG#5: Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies and TG#6: EU Initiatives</i> <i>The data owner will oversee data governance, ensure compliance with Horizon Europe guidelines, and manage data sharing and access permissions.</i></p> <p>2. Copyright Owner <i>Splorotech SL (SPLORO) will retain the copyright for the datasets and any associated documentation created within the project.</i> <i>In collaborative datasets where multiple project partners contribute (e.g., through surveys or focus groups), joint copyright ownership will apply, based on contributions as agreed in the Consortium Agreement.</i> <i>For publications or derivative works, copyright may be shared with co-authors or relevant stakeholders, ensuring proper attribution.</i></p> <p>3. Intellectual Property (IP) Owner <i>Intellectual property rights (IPR) for data, tools, and methodologies developed within the project will follow the principles outlined in the Consortium Agreement:</i> <i>Foreground IP: Newly created IP (e.g., datasets, software tools, algorithms) will belong to the partner(s) generating the specific asset.</i> <i>Background IP: Pre-existing IP contributed by partners will remain the property of the original owner(s), with licenses or access rights granted as needed for project activities.</i> <i>For tools or methodologies co-developed during the project, shared IP ownership may apply as per the Consortium Agreement.</i></p> <p>Special Cases of Data Ownership Participant Data (Survey/Interview Responses) <i>Ownership of the data provided by participants (e.g., survey responses, focus group inputs) remains with the participants themselves.</i> <i>Participants grant the project consortium a non-exclusive license to process and use the data for research purposes, as outlined in the informed consent agreements.</i> Third-Party Data (e.g., Open Calls Data or External Contributions)</p>

		<p>Any data sourced externally or through partnerships (e.g., metadata from EU initiatives) will respect the ownership rights of the original providers. Usage will be governed by licenses or agreements with those entities.</p> <p>Responsibilities of Data Owners</p> <p>Splorotech SPOROTECH SL (SPORO), as the data owner, will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure compliance with data protection laws (e.g., GDPR). • Manage data storage, access, and preservation. • Facilitate data sharing under appropriate licenses, ensuring FAIR principles. • Handle inquiries or disputes related to data ownership and usage rights. <p>Conclusion</p> <p>Ownership of the data, copyright, and intellectual property for the EVOLVE2CARE project will be governed by SPOROTECH SL (SPORO) for the assigned target groups and distributed among contributing partners based on their roles and contributions. This ownership framework ensures proper governance, ethical use, and compliance with Horizon Europe regulations.</p>
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	<p>The data from the EVOLVE2CARE project will primarily be made available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediately for open datasets, to facilitate real-time collaboration and maximize impact. • Within 6 months after project completion for comprehensive datasets, ensuring compliance with quality and ethical standards. • Embargo periods (if any) will be limited to a maximum of 12 months, to support publication and intellectual property protection goals, as required.
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	5 years after the conclusion of the project.

C - Personal Data

If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions

1	What types of personal data will you process?	<p>Contact details of participants in the project research activities and as well as the project partners contact details.</p> <p>We might process personal data by gathering opinions through the interviews and surveys.</p>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	<p>To organize and conducts the research activities, to discuss the project objectives and status of the work with the partners. To contact the participants to the interviews and surveys for our assigned target group</p>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<p>The personal date is relevant to conduct the interview and surveys process. For consortium partners the date is relevant to conduct the work involved in the Evolve2Care project.</p>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Please provide the contact details of your Data Protection Officer (DPO) or a person formally responsible for data protection matters on behalf of your organization.	<p>All the partners are responsible of their assigned target group for the interview and surveys.</p> <p>For Sploro, it will be responsible our internal IT department represented by lopd@sploro.eu</p>
9	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	No

D- Data Security		
1	<p>Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?</p>	<p><i>Storage Locations:</i> Datasets generated during the EVOLVE2CARE project will be stored in a combination of secure cloud storage and certified data repositories.</p> <p><i>Data used and generated through Microsoft office is direct stored in the Microsoft servers. Sensitive or personal data (e.g., participant demographics, survey responses with personal identifiers) will be stored in encrypted, secure cloud environments, such as or Microsoft. These platforms comply with GDPR and other European security regulations.</i></p> <p><i>The data transferred to the consortium SharePoint is stored on the Teams platform servers.</i></p> <p><i>Data shared with the public is stored on EC servers. These repositories comply with European data security standards and are trusted for long-term data storage and accessibility.</i></p> <p><i>The data extracted from survey responses is stored on AUTH's servers.</i></p>
2	<p>What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)</p>	<p><i>Data Security Measures:</i> Encryption: All data, especially sensitive or personal data, will be encrypted both at rest (stored data) and in transit (data being transferred). Storage Encryption: Encryption of datasets through providers systems. Transfer Encryption: Secure transfer protocols (e.g., HTTPS, FTPS) will be used for any data movement between systems or repositories. Backups: Regular backups of the datasets will be conducted to ensure data recovery in case of accidental loss or system failure. Backup data will be encrypted and stored in a separate, secure location. Data Recovery: Procedures will be in place for quick recovery of lost data from backups, ensuring minimal downtime and data loss in case of unforeseen events or disasters.</p>
3	<p>Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?</p>	<p><i>Yes, the datasets will be stored in certified repositories.</i></p>
4	<p>What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?</p>	<p><i>Access Controls:</i> Role-Based Access: Only authorized project members will have access to datasets, based on their roles and the principle of least privilege. Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA): MFA will be used for accessing repositories and cloud storage, ensuring additional layers of security. Audit Trails: Comprehensive logs will be kept for all access to sensitive datasets, including who accessed the data, when, and for what purpose. These logs will be regularly reviewed. Data Access and Transfer: Secure Data Transfer: All sensitive data will be transferred using encrypted channels (e.g., HTTPS, VPNs) to prevent unauthorized interception during the transfer process. Controlled Access to Sensitive Data: Access to sensitive datasets (e.g., personal data) will be restricted, requiring explicit authorization from the data owner or project leader.</p>
5	<p>Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Data Deletion Procedures:</p> <p><i>End of Project:</i> At the conclusion of the project or upon request, any data that is no longer needed or is subject to GDPR rights (e.g., right to be forgotten) will be securely erased.</p> <p><i>Permanent Deletion:</i> Data will be permanently erased from all storage systems following industry best practices. The process will involve secure wiping to ensure that the data cannot be recovered.</p> <p><i>Retention and Erasure Timeline:</i> All unnecessary data will be erased after completion of the processing activities when the purpose of the processing is completed. Following the EC rules necessary data will be retained for additional 5 years after the completion of the project.</p> <p><i>Anonymized or Open Data:</i> Will be kept indefinitely for long-term use and research, unless otherwise specified in the project's data management plan.</p>

		<i>Sensitive or Personal Data: Will be kept for no longer than necessary (typically 5 years post-project) unless required by legal or ethical obligations, after which it will be securely erased in accordance with the retention policy. All these procedures are according to Sploro's internal GDPR policies. Information's at lpd@sploro.eu. <input type="checkbox"/> No</i>
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E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	No

ENOLL

General Information	
Partner Name	European Network of Living Labs
Corresponding person (email)	marta.delosrioswhite@enoll.org , projects@enoll.org

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<p>- <i>Support and Training for Living Labs: Collecting results of open calls and the Living Labs selected enables ENoLL to tailor training programs and provide targeted support during the experimentation phases. This aligns with the objective of empowering Living Labs and enhancing their capacity for real-world impact.</i></p> <p>- <i>Ecosystem Outreach and Clustering: Creating a database of EIT KICs and other relevant initiatives supports the objectives of ecosystem outreach, sustainability, and clustering by identifying potential collaborations, funding opportunities, and synergies.</i></p> <p>- <i>Capacity Building through MOOCs (massive open online courses): Collecting data on registered learners, training materials, course completion statistics, and satisfaction surveys ensures the effectiveness and accessibility of the MOOC, fulfilling the objective of capacity building within the innovation ecosystem.</i></p>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: Data on Living Labs that apply to the open calls, including their profiles, proposed activities, and outcomes of the selection process. This includes confidential data and personal data.</i></p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database: Information on EIT KICs and other relevant initiatives, such as organizational details, areas of focus, and potential for collaboration. This includes personal data of contact points.</i></p> <p><i>MOOC Data: Information about registered learners, training materials used, course progress, completion statistics, and user feedback.</i></p>
3	Please list all the data sets that you process (or plan to process) during the project implementation.	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: Details of applicants (e.g., Living Lab names, location, focus areas), legal information, bank account details)</i></p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database: Profiles of EIT KICs and initiatives (e.g., organization name, sector, funding opportunities, location).</i></p> <p><i>MOOC Data: Learner registration data (e.g., names, email addresses, demographics), training materials, course interaction data, and completion metrics.</i></p>
4	What is the purpose of processing each of the dataset(s) you listed above?	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: To identify and support Living Labs that will participate in the experimentation phase and monitor their progress throughout the project.</i></p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database: To map and facilitate collaborations, ensure sustainability, and foster clustering within the innovation ecosystem.</i></p> <p><i>MOOC Data: To monitor learner participation, measure the effectiveness of the course, improve training materials, and report on project impact.</i></p>
5	Please list all the data attributes for each dataset you listed above and describe each of the attributes.	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Living Lab Name: Name of the applicant.</i> • <i>Location: Geographical location of the Living Lab.</i> • <i>Focus Area: The thematic area addressed by the Living Lab.</i> • <i>Contract details: Contract ID, start and end date, funding amount awarded, payment terms.</i>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Deliverables / Activities:</i> List of expected deliverables, activities and/or milestones agreed. • <i>Contact information:</i> primary contact name, email, address, phone number. • <i>Legal and administrative information:</i> Tax ID or VAT number, legal entity name, signed agreement. • <i>IP Clauses:</i> Information about IP ownership and rights related to the project deliverables. • <i>Data Sharing Agreements:</i> Consent for sharing anonymized data or aggregated reports for the project. • <i>Living Labs proposed activities</i> <p><i>Ecosystem Database:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Organization Name:</i> Name of the EIT KIC or relevant initiative. • <i>Sector:</i> Area of specialization (e.g., mobility, health, energy). • <i>Location:</i> Country or region of operation. • <i>Collaboration Potential:</i> Relevance to ENoLL's sustainability objectives. <p><i>MOOC Data:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Learner Name:</i> Name of the individual registering for the course. • <i>Email Address:</i> Contact information for the learner. • <i>Demographics:</i> (optional) Age, gender, location, or occupation. • <i>Course Statistics:</i> Modules completed, scores, feedback, etc.
6	What formats of data will you generate/collect?	<p><i>Structured Data:</i> CSV, XLSX (e.g., ecosystem database).</p> <p><i>Text Data:</i> DOCX, PPT, PDF (e.g., training materials).</p> <p><i>Usage Metrics:</i> XLSV, CSV (e.g., MOOC statistics).</p> <p><i>Multimedia Data:</i> MP4, AVI (e.g., training videos, recorded webinars)</p>
7	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We will leverage the existing ENoLL databases, specifically the database of active members and the database of active participants in the Health & Wellbeing Working Group (WG), to facilitate the dissemination of questionnaires, open calls, and information about project activities.
8	What is the origin of the data?	<p><i>ENoLL Databases:</i> Previously existing.</p> <p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners:</i> Generated within the project.</p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database:</i> Generated within the project.</p> <p><i>MOOC Data:</i> Generated within the project.</p>
9	What is the expected size of the data?	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners:</i> 1 GB</p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database:</i> 1 GB</p> <p><i>MOOC Data:</i> 10 GB</p>
10	Please explain to whom your datasets will be shared once your processing activities are complete.	Evolve2Care partners, project officer and evaluators
11	To whom might the data be useful?	Evolve2Care partners, project officer and evaluators
12	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Contracts and MOOC, anonymized personal data, data minimisation principle.

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data

B1 - Making data Findable

1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners:</i> name of the Living Lab, geographic location, thematic focus, key stakeholders involved, and key project details.</p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database:</i> names of initiatives, thematic relevance, geographic scope, focus areas, and clustering objectives.</p> <p><i>MOOC Data:</i> anonymized learner IDs, demographics, registration dates, course progress, completion rates, and details of training materials.</p>
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): Dublin Core Metadata Standard <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	N/A
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

B2 - Making data openly accessible

1	Accessibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Public data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Confidential data	
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	<i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: Data includes sensitive information about participating organizations and individuals.</i> <i>Ecosystem Database: Detailed information may include proprietary or sensitive data shared by initiatives.</i> <i>MOOC Data: Includes personal learner data, which must remain private.</i>	
3	How will the data be made accessible	<i>Aggregated and anonymized data will be shared via secure project reports or secured platforms. Non anonymised data of the open call will be collected by SPORO and transferred to ENoLL for the contract. Specifics of data transfer within the two partners are under discussion</i>	
4	Which repository will be used?	Evolve2Care SharePoint – AUTH in charge	
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	Standard tools for spreadsheets, text, PDFs, and video players.	
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): <i>not applicable</i>	
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	Evolve2Care SharePoint – AUTH in charge	
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	Project partners through signed Consortium Agreement	
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No	
11	Are there well-described conditions for access (e.g. a machine-readable license, etc.)?	No	
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	By requiring registration and approval through secure login systems.	
B3 - Making data interoperable			
1	File format	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON Image: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	Dublin Core Metadata Standard	
B4 - Increase data re-use			
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	CC-BY-NC license or CC-BY-NC-ND (in case of MOOC)	
2	Data owner	<i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: ENoLL</i> <i>Ecosystem Database: ENoLL</i> <i>MOOC Data: ENoLL and other partners involved</i>	
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	After the project ends, personal data is anonymised, and confidentiality concerns are addressed.	
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):	
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	At least five years after the project's conclusion.	
C - Personal Data			
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions			
1	What types of personal data will you process?	<i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: Names, contact details (email, phone), professional affiliations, and signed agreements.</i>	

		<p><i>Ecosystem Database: Names, contact details (email, phone), roles within organizations, and affiliations to Living Labs.</i></p> <p><i>MOOC Data: Names, email addresses, learner profiles, statistics on course completion (e.g., progress data).</i></p>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: To formalize contractual agreements and maintain communication during the project implementation phases.</i></p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database: To maintain a database of stakeholders for ecosystem outreach, clustering, and sustainability purposes.</i></p> <p><i>MOOC Data: To monitor learner progress, provide access to course materials, and track training outcomes.</i></p>
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: Only necessary data is collected to ensure compliance with contractual obligations and to communicate with awarded Living Labs.</i></p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database: Personal data collected is limited to facilitating collaborations and outreach with relevant ecosystem stakeholders.</i></p> <p><i>MOOC Data: Data collected is limited to learner profiles and training statistics required for monitoring and evaluation.</i></p>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <i>using the existing ENoLL databases to promote participation in related activities.</i> <input type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <i>data may be shared with project partners as required by the contract, using secure platforms (e.g., SharePoint).</i> <input type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <i>contracts contain sensitive data, terms and conditions that are confidential and cannot be shared beyond authorized parties.</i> <input type="checkbox"/> No
8	Please provide the contact details of your Data Protection Officer (DPO) or a person formally responsible for data protection matters on behalf of your organization.	<p><i>Privacy@enoll.org</i></p>
9	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	<p><i>Compliance with GDPR in handling personal data, and compliance with confidentiality clauses in contracts</i></p>

D- Data Security		
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	<p><i>All datasets will be stored in the project repository managed by the project coordinator (AUTH).</i></p> <p><i>Contracts with Open Call Winners: Secure cloud storage with limited access to authorized personnel. Stored in the project repository managed by the project coordinator (AUTH).</i></p> <p><i>Ecosystem Database: Secure cloud storage with limited access to authorized personnel. Stored in the project repository managed by the project coordinator (AUTH).</i></p> <p><i>MOOC Data: MOOC platform servers and secure cloud storage with restricted access to administrators. Stored in the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy (academy.enoll.org) managed by ENoLL.</i></p>
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	<p><i>Data is encrypted during transfer and stored in password-protected systems with regular backups to ensure data integrity and recovery.</i></p>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	<p>Yes,</p>
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	<p><i>ENoLL will potentially store data for internal analysis and processing on the Sharepoint area specifically dedicated to the Evolve2care. The provision of this ENoLL-restricted space is an in-kind contribution of ENoLL as part of its Microsoft 365 Business license.</i></p> <p><i>Access to the area is limited to ENoLL staff working on the project activities, financial and administrative management, and quality supervision.</i></p> <p><i>Data are securely stored with robust encryption and access controls on EU-based servers.</i></p> <p><i>All data are securely stored utilizing ENoLL-licenced cloud-based storage with robust encryption and access controls whose servers are located in the EU.</i></p>

		<i>Microsoft Teams complies with the GDPR through data protection measures, encryption, audits, and strict processing agreements.</i>
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <i>Yes, data is deleted upon the end of retention periods or at the request of the data subject, following GDPR compliance.</i> <input type="checkbox"/> No

E - Other Issues		
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?	<i>Project-specific guidelines and ENoLL's internal data management procedures.</i>

VII

General Information	
Partner Name	ViLabs (CY) LTD
Corresponding person (email)	Vassilis Voulgarakis (vmvoulga@vilabs.eu)

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<i>Dissemination and Communication efforts' documentation in the context of outreach and clustering activities</i>
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	Databases and reports The databases will entail text data referring to activities' details and the implementing partners; numeric data regarding the target groups engaged/reached and URL links to external websites (if applicable, e.g., link to a conference web portal, link to publishing platform)
3	Please list all the data sets that you process (or plan to process) during the project implementation.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Outreach activities reporting forms</i> <i>Outreach activities monitoring databases</i> <i>Outreach activities assessment reports</i>
4	What is the purpose of processing each of the dataset(s) you listed above?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Collect the efforts and each project beneficiary in standardised and uniformed manner</i> <i>Keep track of project's efforts to meet outreach goals and milestones</i> <i>Produce input for project's deliverables and progress reports</i>
5	Please list all the data attributes for each dataset you listed above and describe each of the attributes.	<i>Standardised reporting forms and databases including reporting fields such as:</i> <i>Implementing partner; date; type of activity; URL link(s), audiovisual material, attendance and/or traffic (for online activities)</i>
6	What formats of data will you generate/collect?	<i>.xlsx .docx and .pdf file formats</i>
7	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <i>Data such as conference proceedings where citations of project's outputs are entailed, will be documented for reporting purposes of the project. Audiovisual content from third-party organisers of events where the project is disseminated will be stored and featured at project's online channels and reporting.</i>
8	What is the origin of the data?	<i>Please Specify: The aggregated data will come from partners' reporting forms.</i>
9	What is the expected size of the data?	<i>Please Specify</i>
10	Please explain to whom your datasets will be shared once your processing activities are complete.	<i>Project Consortium Project Officer(s) and European Commission's reviewing parties Public (only for publicly available deliverables upon their approval by EC)</i>
11	To whom might the data be useful?	<i>Any reader/reviewer of the foreseen project's deliverables and progress reports, who seeks to learn more about the project's outreach and clustering efforts</i>
12	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <i>The aggregated data will strictly correspond to the required information (predefined by the reporting forms). The reporting form is reflective of the input requested by EC reporting</i>

	mechanisms, while the collection of personal data (such as names, gender, etc.) is not part of the reporting forms fields.
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B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data					
B1 - Making data Findable					
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
2	What metadata will be created?				
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): N/A				
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how The aggregated data are going to be presented in the project's public reports, where efforts are going to be reported in detailed manner.				
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
B2 - Making data openly accessible					
1	Accessibility <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> data				
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why Data related to project's monitoring of efforts shall not be disclosed without specific reason/request by authorized groups				
3	How will the data be made accessible Data that will be included in the project's public deliverables will be accessible				
4	Which repository will be used? Project's repository for internal monitoring Project's Zenodo community for publicly available deliverables and reports				
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Standard MS Office tools will be used for processing the data retrieved from the reporting forms.				
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): N/A				
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? N/A				
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided? Prior to the publication of project report deliverables where the data are presented in detail, access to the data is limited to authorized personnel employed by the project partners for the implementation of EVOLVE2CARE project. The partners' personnel are the only individuals with access to the project's repository where the aggregated data will be stored.				
10	Is there a need for a data access committee? N/A				
11	Are there well-described conditions for access (e.g. a machine-readable license, etc.)? The project's GA enshrines the rules for data accessibility.				
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? Project partners' teams are granted access to datasets stored at project's repository				
B3 - Making data interoperable					
File format					
1	<table border="1"> <tr> <td> Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML </td> <td> Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON </td> <td> Image: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ </td> <td> Other (please specify): </td> </tr> </table>	Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data: <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data: <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):		
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow? N/A				
B4 - Increase data re-use					

1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	N/A
2	Data owner	VIL as the assigned Task Leader
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	Data will be openly accessible for potential re-use once the EC mechanisms approve the submitted deliverables, where the data are presented.
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): The aggregated data do not present intrinsic scientific and/or technical value for third parties. They shall serve specific effort's reporting and documentation needs within the context of the project implementation.
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	All data will be available in the deliverables that must be available at least 5 years after completion of the project

C - Personal Data

If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions

1	What types of personal data will you process?	<i>The collection of personal data will be kept at minimum necessity and will be opted only in specific occasions such as the documentation of partners' contribution to scientific and technical events (e.g., conference paper submission, panel participation, etc.) Professional and job-function related information will be collected on the basis of the reporting needs (i.e., target groups engaged/reached by an activity).</i>
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	See above
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	<i>The collection of personal data, albeit limited and conditional, is going to be carried out in compliance with GDPR regulations, while the persons of interested will be notified about this collection and the corresponding terms of use and privacy policy. The personal data will not be subject to any kind of subsequent editing and/or modification, apart from the necessary preparations of the communication activities of the project (e.g., posting a news item on the project's website, or making a post at project's social media pages) and the official project's reports.</i>
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
8	Please provide the contact details of your Data Protection Officer (DPO) or a person formally responsible for data protection matters on behalf of your organization.	Vicky Mouttzi (mova@vilabs.eu)
9	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	N/A

D- Data Security

1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	Project's repository for internal monitoring
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	The project's repository is operated by the coordination (AUTH) <i>All applicable security configurations are applied and the access is permitted only upon invitation by the coordination team</i>
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): History of changes and document review mode are available at project's repository. Predefined history of changes table is set for all project's deliverables including those linked with the reporting of dissemination and communication activities. ViLabs infrastructure also

	hosts an internal repository where the data will be safeguarded according to the organisation’s secured processes. No unauthorised personnel and/or external parties will be granted access to the collected data. <input type="checkbox"/> No
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E - Other Issues	
1	Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? N/A

AV

General Information	
Partner Name	Anthology Ventures
Corresponding person (email)	kb@anthologyventures.com , pg@anthologyventures.com , at@anthologyventures.com

A – Data Summary		
1	What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	The purpose of data collection or generation in a project is to provide the foundational information needed to address research questions, solve problems, or achieve specific objectives. Depending on the nature of the project, data collection or generation serves various roles, including informed decision-making, validation of hypotheses, identifying patterns and trends, model building and predictions, problem solving etc. As for its objectives, the data collection and generation will facilitate the technology upscaling through the training programs (KO1), the commercialization through the dissemination and communication campaigns (KO2), the demonstration of pan-European testing (KO3) and the knowledge sharing by facilitating the collaboration through the AccelUP platform (KO4).
2	What types of data you will generate/collect?	The data that will be generated will be quantitative (e.g., numerical health metrics), and qualitative (e.g.interviews).
3	Please list all the data sets that you process (or plan to process) during the project implementation.	The datasets that we plan to process are indicatively a) types of services offered from Living Labs, b) investment data in the healthcare sector, healthtech innovators data on type of innovations, innovation potential and maturity level. Further data sets will be defined later as the project progresses (i.e. data from healthcare providers, patients, community, regulatory authorities).
4	What is the purpose of processing each of the dataset(s) you listed above?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) types of services offered from Living Labs – this data set will provide information on how we can cohesively systematize the services offered from LLs around Europe to enable innovators utilize infrastructure and expertise around Europe. This systematization will be provided through ACCELUP platform b) investment data in the healthcare sector – this data set will provide insight on the investment trends in the healthcare sector and will help LLs formulate services to innovators that can increase investment readiness c) healthtech innovators data – this data will assist on understanding the needs of innovators in the sector and inform the service providers i.e. the LLs
5	Please list all the data attributes for each dataset you listed above and describe each of the attributes.	Survey Responses Data from Open Calls Focus Group Minutes Interview Data
6	What formats of data will you generate/collect?	xlsx, doc, pdf

7	Will you re-use any existing data and how?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes : By reusing data from publicly available sources on investors in the healthtech sector.
8	What is the origin of the data?	The origin of the data will be the surveys, the workshops, the interview Data, the reports, the Living Labs and the various stakeholders (healthcare providers, patients etc)
9	What is the expected size of the data?	Not known
10	Please explain to whom your datasets will be shared once your processing activities are complete.	The datasets will be made available after processed through online repositories to the public, to the project partners, to the Journal and Conference Publications, to the European Commission and to any stakeholder interested.
11	To whom might the data be useful?	The data will be useful to any pertinent healthcare research group, to educational institutes, to private and public sector and lastly to the public.
12	Will you apply data aggregation, minimization and anonymization methods to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): We plan to apply data minimization by processing only data that will be necessary for the project and not more than that.

B - FAIR Data - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable Data		
B1 - Making data Findable		
1	Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
2	What metadata will be created?	Publications that will include processed anonymized data
3	Do metadata standards exist in your discipline? ^{ix}	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): N/A
4	In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how	N/A
5	Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
B2 - Making data openly accessible		
1	Accessibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
2	If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why	Specific datasets concerning the implementation and the disclosure of project's objectives may be subject to strict legal and proprietary restrictions.
3	How will the data be made accessible	The data will be accessible through the project's deliverables, presentation materials and publications
4	Which repository will be used?	Organisational repositories provided by Google, Zenodo, and project's website platform will be used for accessing the project's public data.
5	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?	N/A
6	Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
7	Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No (please specify): N/A
8	Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	The data will be deposited in Zenodo and project's website.
9	If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?	N/A
10	Is there a need for a data access committee?	No
11	Are there well-described conditions for access (e.g. a machine-readable license, etc.)?	N/A
12	How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	The identity of a person will be ascertained through the project partners' codes and social media teams that have been created and distributed to all of the members.
B3 - Making data interoperable		
	File format	

1	<p>Spreadsheet:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV</p> <p>Documentation:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PDF</p>	<p>Structured data:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON</p> <p>Geographical data:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON</p>	<p>Image:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PNG</p> <p>Video:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MP4</p>	<p>Other (please specify):</p>
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	<input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML		<input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	
2	What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow?	N/A		
B4 - Increase data re-use				
1	How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?	The data generated within the project will be available through the open repository for EU-funded research outputs from Horizon Europe, Zenodo.		
2	Data owner	The owners would be all of the project's consortium partners.		
3	When will the data be made available for re-use?	The data will be available for re-use after the end of the project.		
4	Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (please specify):		
5	How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?	N/A		

C - Personal Data				
If you are going to process personal data, please answer the following questions				
1	What types of personal data will you process?	The types of personal data that will be process during the project will be email addresses, research notes and interviews.		
2	What is the reason of processing the personal data?	The reason of processing personal data is for contacting project partners and for conducting interviews necessary for research purposes.		
3	May you explain how the personal data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project?	The personal data is relevant to conduct the interview and surveys process.		
4	Will you process any special categories of personal data within the meaning of Art. 9 GDPR?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		
5	Will you process previously collected personal data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		
6	Are you going to transfer/share your data? If so, where and how will you transfer your data?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		
7	Will you process any data that cannot be shared?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		
8	Please provide the contact details of your Data Protection Officer (DPO) or a person formally responsible for data protection matters on behalf of your organization.	Mr. Argyrios Spyridis, as@anthologyventures.com		
9	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?	NO		

D- Data Security				
1	Where will the datasets be stored or are already stored?	The datasets will be stored into internal repositories provided by Google, which provides built-in security automatically detecting and preventing online threats, thereby providing confidence that information is safe.		
2	What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)	Please check the answer provided above		
3	Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes, the datasets will be stored in certified repositories provided by Google.		
4	What security measures will be implemented to prevent unauthorised access to data (including personal data) or the equipment used for processing?	A unique invitation from the coordination team is sent to any project member in order to access the repository and the social media platforms.		
5	Do you have procedures for erasure and deletion of data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (please specify): <u>End of Project:</u> At the conclusion of the project or upon request, any data that is no longer needed or is subject to GDPR rights will be securely erased. <u>Permanent Erasure:</u> In accordance with industry best practices, data will be permanently removed from all storage systems. To guarantee that the data cannot be recovered, the procedure will		

		<p>include secure wiping. <u>Retention and Erasure Timeline:</u> Unless otherwise noted in the project's data management plan, anonymized or open data will be retained indefinitely for purposes of research and long-term use. Sensitive or personal data will be securely deleted in compliance with the retention policy after being retained for no longer than necessary, usually five years after the project, unless mandated by legal or ethical requirements.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/>No</p>
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E - Other Issues

1	<p>Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?</p>	N/A
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- ⁱ State the purpose of the data collection/generation.
 - ⁱⁱ Define the nature of the data, e.g. quantitative, qualitative, numeric, text, audio, structured, unstructured, etc.
 - ⁱⁱⁱ Define the format of the data, e.g. txt, xlsx, doc, pdf, etc.
 - ^{iv} Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any).
 - ^v Specify the origin of the data.
 - ^{vi} State the expected size of the data (if known).
 - ^{vii} Outline the data utility, to whom will it be useful, e.g. research groups, private sector, citizens, etc.
 - ^{viii} Define if privacy preservation techniques are required before making your data open.
 - ^{ix} Define the metadata standards you use. Link regarding the metadata standards:
<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/list>.
 - ^x Outline the approach towards search keyword (e.g. search keywords will be provided when the dataset will be uploaded to the repository).
 - ^{xi} Will data produced and/or used in the project be made openly available?
 - ^{xii} If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.
 - ^{xiii} Specify how the data will be made available, e.g. by deposition in a repository.
 - ^{xiv} Specify which repository will you use, e.g. Zenodo, open-access journal, project website, etc.
 - ^{xv} E.g. Zenodo, open-access journal, project website, etc.
 - ^{xvi} Specify why.
 - ^{xvii} License conditions: Copyright, Creative Commons, Open License, etc. A list of licenses can be found here
<https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>
 - ^{xviii} List the data owner, the copyright owner, the intellectual property owner.
 - ^{xix} E.g. Immediately, after the end of the project (specify the exact time), along with the publication of main results, etc. If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
 - ^{xx} If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.
 - ^{xxi} Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable, e.g. 5 years after the conclusion of the project.
 - ^{xxii} E.g. email addresses, phone numbers, affiliation, position, research notes, interviews
 - ^{xxiii} E.g. for contacting project partners, for conduct interviews necessary for research purposes
 - ^{xxiv} Special categories of data are personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation
 - ^{xxv} If yes, you should collect evidence that previous beneficiary has lawfully processed the data and applied appropriate technical and organizational measures for securing data.
 - ^{xxvi} Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data.
 - ^{xxvii} Indicate if you must adhere to other policies and procedures for data management.